

DEPARTMENT OF INFORMATICS

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT MÜNCHEN

Bachelor's Thesis in Informatics: Games Engineering

**Virtual Reality Systems for Serious Games on
the subject of dive simulation**

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Virtual Reality Systeme für Serious Games am Beispiel Tauchsimulation

Virtual Reality Systems for Serious Games on the subject of dive simulation

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I confirm that this bachelor's thesis in informatics: games engineering is my own work and I have documented all sources and material used.

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Abstract

With Virtual Reality (VR) technology maturing and spreading widely in recent years, it is becoming an increasingly useful tool for entertainment and education. Its potential to simulate hard to reach environments and emulate unique experiences believably is of great interest, in particular for recreational and professional diving. Many of the world's most intriguing archaeological sites are located in the planet's oceans and are only accessible to experienced divers and underwater archaeologists. VR could provide an immersive way for everyone to enjoy Underwater Cultural Heritage and the sport of diving from their own home or as a museum exhibit.

This thesis provides a detailed look at VR Systems and their use for Serious Games, focusing on their application for immersive diving simulation. An overview of the field of VR, its current state of the art, and its usefulness in Serious Games is provided as a foundation for the design of our own simulation system. To assess the possibility and challenges of recreating diving in VR, the sport is examined in detail and a gameplay and technological design for an immersive VR diving simulator is proposed. A prototype of the simulator was developed following the suggested design, along with a questionnaire to evaluate its immersion and effectivity as a diver trainer and educational tool.

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1. Introduction

The year 2020 saw the rise of the COVID-19 pandemic, which quickly disrupted our day-to-day life in a number of ways. After initial containment fails and the virus began spreading in many countries, Germany and other countries began to enact first regional, then nationwide lockdowns, confining everyone to their home. Businesses had to switch to working at home where possible, schools to online classes, while centers of cultural and societal discourse (e.g. museums and art galleries, were closed entirely). Almost two years later, in 2021, people have somewhat returned to normal life, but the way we approach interpersonal contact, shared culture and professional communication has changed.

During the numerous lockdowns more people than ever were confronted with the virtual world of computers and the world wide web. For many *Zoom*, *Skype*, and *Discord* became synonymous with social exchange and some began to seek alternatives to their hobbies and pastimes. Even though online pub nights, browser-based escape rooms and online games were fun, and video chat meetings were more natural than email chains, many missed the real feeling of presence in their social interactions. Certain activities sports or visiting museum exhibits are impossible to recreate well by using traditional 2D monitors and keyboard, mouse or controller inputs.

A month into the first lockdown in Germany, I found myself bored with the small library of games I had for my Valve Index Virtual Reality (VR) headset and decided to try out a new free to play game called "*A Township Tale*". In this multiplayer role playing game, the player has to explore an open world and use resources to build a town collaboratively [1]. Within the first hour of playing the game's tutorial, I encountered two other players who are represented by a flying torso, two articulated arms, and a head. Despite the relatively simplistic graphics, the sense of social presence and immersion created by the VR game felt more realistic and less exhausting than other virtual social interactions and even video chats.

The combination of Three Dimensional (3D) images, the large and encompassing Field of View (FOV), and the natural and intuitive interaction awarded by VR, has the potential to create immersive virtual experiences that replicate real world environments and activities realistically anywhere in the world [2]. VR hardware is becoming more widely adopted and with multiple large companies investing in the technology, the barrier of entry is lowered even further through cheaper headsets and better availability [3].

Museums and institutions of cultural heritage in particular could profit from VR by using its immersive nature to make otherwise only locally accessible exhibits and environments available to more people. Lowering the effort required to access these resources could poten-

tially raise interest in these aforementioned cultural properties and sites and, once combined with aspects of Serious Games (SGs), provide playful education to the general public.

One field in particular impacted by the lockdowns was diving tourism and Underwater Cultural Heritage (UCH). Museums and public places dedicated to UCH were closed and many diving destinations could no longer be reached by recreational or professional divers due to international travel restrictions. However, even without travel restrictions, recreational diving is not an activity available to everyone, as it requires training, equipment, and the ability to travel to the diving site. Additionally, some diving spots are located in restricted waters or in dangerous locations, requiring further permissions or training. Due to the majority of the Earth's surface being covered in water, many beautiful environments and remnants of human history are located underwater, and by extension unavailable to a majority of the population. These sites hold great educational value, but are hard to investigate due to their difficulty of access.

As Professional Association of Diving Instructors (PADI) trained divers, my colleague Guy Kost and I believe VR is a promising tool for an approachable recreation of the diving experience anywhere and holds great value for research of hard to access UCH. In this thesis we aim to evaluate the viability of an immersive VR System to realistically simulate the act of diving in a Serious Game (SG). We propose a design for an immersive VR diving simulation system based on realistic physical simulation and rules provided by the PADI in order to explore how and to what extent aspects of diving can be recreated in VR. A prototype of the design was created as a test-bed, alongside a user study which was designed to evaluate the immersion of the simulator and its ability to convey knowledge relating to the fields of diving and UCH. The design and the prototype in particular were created in cooperation with Guy Kost. While this thesis places a larger focus on the design and technological aspects of VR and the dive simulation, Kost's paper [4] details the role of game mechanics in SGs and discusses our combined work from a ludo-narrative perspective while also expanding on some points only tangentially mentioned here.

1.1. History of Virtual Reality

VR has fascinated humans for a long time now and while many today might associate the term with modern Head-Mounted Display (HMD)s, omnidirectional treadmills, or brain-computer interfaces, this has not always been the case.

The term "virtual reality" first appeared in the book *The Theater and its Double*, published in 1958, which used the term to describe the items and characters in a theatre play as opposed to humans and objects in real life. The concept of VR however is even older. The aforementioned book was actually a translation of the french *Le Théâtre et son double* by Antonin Artaud which was released twenty years prior, which used "la réalité virtuelle" to describe the same. [5]

Yet even before these books, ideas and machines, similar to modern VR Systems, can be found in various stages of design: from theoretical paper to fully functioning system. In 1929, Edwin Albert Link invented the *Link Trainer*, an early yet revolutionary flight simulation system that relied on mechanical engineering to simulate the act of flying an airplane. It was used to great extent during the Second World War in many different countries aiding in the safe training for hundreds of thousands of pilots [6].

With the beginning of the *Pulp Era* and the *Golden Age of Science Fiction*, concepts of VR found their way into an increasing number of books. The earliest example of such a story is *Pygmalion's Spectacles* published 1935 by Stanley G. Weinbaum, in which a movie can be experienced by means of a pair of special goggles, which can be used to experience a virtual environment through the senses of sight, sound, taste, smell, and touch [7, 8].

In 1955, Morton Heilig published *The Cinema of the Future* in which he described an "Experience Theater", that extended the experience to multiple senses instead of only vision. Years later, he built a working prototype of the machine, the *Sensorama*, which could display images in stereoscopic 3D colour vision, play stereo audio, disperse smells, generate wind through fans, and motion through a special chair [9, 10]. He went on to invent the *Telesphere Mask*, a predecessor to modern HMDs, which was succeeded a year later, in 1961, by the *Headsight*, the first motion tracked HMD, cementing his legacy as one of the forefathers of modern VR [11].

In 1989, the *EyePhone* was released by *VPL Research* and demonstrated one of the first naturally intractable VR environments through the use of the *DataGlove*, an early partially motion-tracked glove. The HMD could show up to five or six frames per second and was largely unavailable to general consumers due to its high price point of 250.000 dollars [12]. One year later *VPL Research* released the *Virtual Interface Environment Workstation* or *VIEW* in cooperation with *NASA Ames*, a HMD that allowed advanced interaction with the virtual environment by using a *DataGlove* and an early full body tracking device called the *DataSuit* [13].

Over the following twenty years, VR development proceeded slowly, but steadily, with few notable releases or milestones. The company *Virtuality* created multiple VR game systems for arcades and corporations throughout the 1990s that promised an experience closely resembling today's HMDs, making them one of the pioneers of consumer VR technology [14]. Shortly after, famous video game company *Nintendo* released their *Virtual Boy* console - a monochromatic stereoscopic VR HMD - with few games and no head tracking [15]. Both companies had problems with the visual fidelity of their products and therefore not have a big impact on the general entertainment market at the time.

The dawn of modern VR as we know it today began with the announcement of the *Oculus Rift* in 2012, and its subsequent purchase by *Facebook*. The advancements made in visual quality combined with the increased performance allowed for a massive boost in popularity, and for the first time be truly viable as a consumer product. [16]. With further advancements

made by *Valve* [17] and the subsequent cooperation with *HTC*, more companies started to invest in the sector and a growing number of HMDs, with related technologies becoming more available [18]. In the future VR is expected to gain even more popularity, with an expected significant market growth, predictions of cheaper hardware, and improved technological fidelity [3].

1.2. Overview

In this thesis we want to provide an overview of VR Systems and their use in the field of Serious Games, in particular for dive simulation. Initially we provide an extensive overview of the field of VR in order to provide a solid foundation for further discussion. Existing VR Systems and SGs are analysed before the intricacies of dive simulations are laid out. A design for a VR System and SG are proposed and finally an evaluation design is given, before future work and a conclusion completes the paper.

Chapter 2 covers the theoretical background of the paper and provides an overview of the matter. In particular definitions are discussed and set to provide consistency throughout the thesis and important concepts are elaborated upon in further detail.

Chapter 3 highlights existing VR Systems and VR SGs, which are either directly, or tangentially related to the topic of dive simulation and UCH. Each related work is examined in detail to extract information and good practices for use in our own design in chapter 5 and prototype in chapter 6.

Chapter 4 details the specifics of diving and discusses what has to be replicated in the simulation for an authentic simulation and realistic experience.

Chapter 5 proposes a detailed design regarding our own VR System for dive simulation. The underlying design principles are explained before the full design is laid out.

Chapter 6 elaborates on the development of the prototype "*200 Bar*", that has been constructed on the basis of the previously proposed design.

Chapter 7 focuses on the design of an evaluation survey that is intended to assess the prototype's performance along multiple metrics pertaining to its immersion, authenticity, and usefulness as an educational tool.

Chapter 8 is delegated to exploring further developments and research opportunities based on the work done in this thesis. Particularly the future development of the prototype is discussed.

Chapter 9 provides a final conclusion of the research conducted within this thesis.

2. Theoretical Background

In order to discuss VR Systems, SGs, and their combined use for immersive and authentic dive simulation, a number of concepts and technologies require an explanation. This chapter defines commonly used terms and provides an introduction to the topics reoccurring throughout the thesis.

2.1. Definition of Virtual Reality

There are many valid definitions for the concept of Virtual Reality (VR), some more focused on the theoretical or philosophical aspects, others pertaining to the technological background. In this section we want to shortly examine VR from different angles and propose a definition that is used in the following paper.

The term originates from the words "virtual" and "reality", the former meaning "[...] something in essence or effect, though not actually or in fact" [19] and the latter "real existence, what is real, the aggregate of all that is real" [20]. Together they form an oxymoron, "something that is real, but in a way that is not actually real" - an impossible concept in theory, except in relation to computers. While computer hardware is fully real and tangible, the data, concepts, and images created by one, are not always considered to be, which over time changed the definition of "virtual" to "not physically existing but made to appear by software" [19]. With this new understanding of "virtual" with regards to computers, VR is no longer a contradictory concept, but rather "an artificial environment experienced through sensory stimuli provided by a computer" (adapted from Merriam-Webster [21]). The term can also be associated with the technology and hardware that is utilised to access or create a virtual reality [21].

Over time an increasing number of technologies were able to produce virtual environments to various degrees of fidelity, some of which were not completely immersive or artificial. These two concepts were associated with VR. To address this, Milgram proposed a new taxonomy system in 1994: Mixed Reality (MR) and the Virtuality Continuum. This taxonomy classifies certain technologies that were not fully immersive or did not use completely virtual environments as separated subclasses and popularised the terms such as Augmented Reality (AR), which are still widely in use today.

This is important, as this thesis specifically excludes AR and MR, focusing only on "true" VR that is used to create experiences and environments "[...] in which the participant-observer is totally immersed in, and able to interact with, a completely synthetic world" [22].

In addition to the abstract nature of the topic, this thesis also focuses on the hardware and software utilised for and in connection with VR. For that reason we want to highlight an alternative, technology-centred definition:

"[...] VR can be properly defined as a complex technology which exploits more low-level technologies (such as computer science, 3D graphics, robotics etc.) in order to create a digital environment which users feel completely immersed inside, and which they may interact with." [23]

To fit the specific nature of this thesis, an extended definition was created, based on the work done by Carrozzino et al. [23], which also including the previously mentioned more abstract definitions. As both concepts go hand in hand and sometimes transition fluidly, it would be impractical to separate them into individual terms. The final definition of VR is therefore as follows:

Virtual Reality (VR) is defined as a complex technology which exploits more low-level technologies in order to create an entirely virtual environment which users feel completely immersed inside, and which they may interact with, and the created immersive virtual environment itself.

2.1.1. Virtual Reality Systems

Following our previous definition, the term "VR System" describes a specific collection of technologies working together to create an immersive virtual environment that can be interacted with, as well as the resulting virtual experience itself. Such a system usually consist of a combination of hardware and software, which can be individually described without context or relation to other parts of the system for an in depth discussion of the technology utilised. To form a valid description of the whole VR System however, the interaction of the underlying technologies and sub-systems must be further elaborated; in particular the role in the overall system as well as the relationship with each other. One specific instance or variation of a VR System based on certain settings or setups within the structure is called a configuration.

2.1.2. Virtual Reality Hardware

VR hardware is manifold and can not always be easily classified into set categories. When considering the topic from a theoretical perspective, any piece of hardware, both in the classical understanding of computer related hardware (e.g. mouse, keyboard, monitor, HMD, etc.) and physical devices or objects in general (e.g. a box, a climbing harness, etc.), can be part of a VR System and therefore be considered VR hardware in that specific context.

Two of the most well known VR devices are likely the Head-Mounted Display (HMD) and the Cave Automatic Virtual Environment (CAVE). The former is a wearable display situated

directly on the face of the user akin to a pair of glasses, blocking their entire field of vision to display the virtual environment in front of both eyes. It is often coupled with some form of motion tracking and handheld controllers used for interaction in VR [18]. The latter is a room of variable size, that displays images on multiple of its sides to immerse the user in the virtual environment. [24]. An in depth comparison of both is performed in chapter 5 highlighting their strengths and weaknesses.

Carrozzino et al. [23] offer a taxonomy that fits in with their technology based definition of VR highlighted in section 2.1, classifying various VR hardware into two major categories, which are further subdivided along an axis for more detailed distinction. The first category classifies VR devices that are used to interact with a virtual environment by their quality of interaction provided. The axis ranges from non-interactive, over device based interaction, to natural interaction, arranging the devices in four loose groups, as shown in figure 2.1.

The second category classifies VR devices that are used to experience a virtual environment based on their level of provided immersion. Devices are further grouped into four classes according to the senses they stimulate and again arranged in a similar fashion to the interaction classification, which can be seen in figure 2.2.

Interaction

Figure 2.1.: Classification of VR devices on the interaction axis.

Source: Carrozzino et al. [23]

It is of note that the devices within figures 2.1 and 2.2 were arranged based on the technology available during the publication of the paper (2010) and certain hardware might have to be moved along the axis to represent their current state of the art. Especially Head-Mounted Display (HMD) technology has improved greatly with the release of the *Oculus Rift CV1* and should therefore be of a similar level of immersion as the Cave Automatic Virtual Environment (CAVE) [16, 25]. Throughout this paper we will focus primarily on technology with higher levels of immersion, for reasons explained below, and therefore, in relation to hardware, VR usually refers to those devices, unless stated otherwise.

Immersion

Figure 2.2.: Classification of VR devices on the immersion axis.

Source: Carrozzino et al. [23]

2.2. The Role of Immersion

To outline the impact of immersion on games, three concepts, immersion, presence, and interactivity, have to be defined first and their relationship has to be described. Immersion itself as a term is hard to define and has historically described two different, but related concepts:

- The technological or sensory fidelity a VR system provides, often pertaining to the hardware. [2]
- Feeling completely absorbed and enveloped by the virtual environment, a psychological state of mind. [26]

In relation to the topic in this thesis, we adopt the notion proposed by Mütterlein [26], which classifies immersion as a psychological experience, that, while definitely influenced and confined by the technological fidelity of the system, has to be evaluated and measured on a subjective level. This mixed definition also more heavily considers the role of flow [27] in immersion, a viewpoint entirely absent from the purely technological point of view, without excluding the importance of the latter entirely [2, 28].

Presence is more universally agreed upon as subjective psychological response and is defined as the feeling or experience of being in a location or environment, even when physically located somewhere else [26, 2].

Interactivity is considered to be another key feature in the examination of VR and refers to the ability of players in VR to interact with the digital environment.

Presence and immersion are generally considered to be linked, often to a point where an individual distinction is hard to make out [26, 28]. Interactivity on the other hand is sometimes considered to have no influence on immersion whatsoever, especially when viewed from a technological perspective [2]. Recent studies however have found evidence for distinct links between interaction and immersion, as well as presence [29, 30], especially in cases, where a more psychological and distinct definition of immersion was used [26].

While further research has to be conducted to fully understand the complex relationship of all three concepts, their influence on user experience is better understood. High levels of immersion and presence are linked to better user experience [26, 30], improved performance in certain tasks [31], better spatial understanding [2], and can positively contribute to flow [32]. Studies on the effect of interaction also offer partial evidence for positive effects on learning [33], which are further highlighted in the next section. Generally it can be said that immersion, presence, and interactivity have a variety of positive effects and have to be considered and optimised for when creating a VR System.

Finally, we want to note that, even though Mütterlein's final definition proposes a clear distinction between immersion and interactivity [26], in the specific case of dive simulation presence in the virtual underwater environment could be considered to be part of the diving activity itself. For this and the fact that diving simulation can profit of heightened technological fidelity, as discussed in chapter 4, the term immersion is still occasionally used throughout this thesis in relation to the technological quality and presence, where applicable to the activity of diving, instead of confining it purely to activities.

2.3. Virtual Reality in Serious Games

A Serious Game (SG) is a game with a purposed beyond entertainment, often specifically designed to utilise gameplay to educate, train, or convey information [34]. VR in particular is a technology, that seems to be specifically suited to be used in SGs, promising improved training and more focused education [35]. VR can provide very high levels of immersion and offers natural interactivity, that can not be replicated with traditional desktop PCs [23], possibly facilitating more effective learning in certain situations [33]. Through motion tracking complex physical tasks can be simulated and both traditional education and practical training can be performed within VR to great effect [36].

VR SGs have proven to be effective in medical education, offering improvements over traditional tablet-based SGs [37], and could be of great use in disaster training [38]. Most notably they are a suitable technology for the promotion of cultural content by making remote exhibits more accessible in an authentic and engaging way [23] and can provide unique and interactive educational experiences. This is especially valuable in a time where public places of cultural heritage not always accessible due to lockdowns or travel restrictions [39].

2. Theoretical Background

Based on the apparent success in related fields, we think VR SGs are a fitting technology to simulate diving in a realistic and engaging way. The fully immersive visuals in combination with authentic interaction could be very beneficial for low effort dive training and the strong sense of presence can be used to experience distant real world diving spots without traveling. In particular restricted diving spots or hard to reach UCH sites could be made available to more people, without the need for extensive training.

3. Related Work

In this chapter we want to showcase a number of existing projects in the field of VR, UCH, and SG to discuss their findings and extract information, good practices, and opportunities for our own work.

3.1. The Dawn of Art

The Dawn of Art is a short VR experience released in 2020 by *Atlas V* in cooperation with *The Public Union for the Management of the Chauvet Cave* that allows players to explore a virtual recreation of the *Chauvet Cave* in Ardèche, France [40]. The game's content is largely focused on education and was created to deliver information on the World Heritage site in an interesting and engaging way, which classifies it as a SG despite not being explicitly advertised as such [41].

Players have the option to choose between two experiences, an immersive 360 degree film and a virtual tour of the cave as it is today. The immersive film is situated circa 36.000 years in the past and aims to put players in the role of an early human, who arrives at the cave and explores it for the first time. A guiding voiceover by Daisy Ridley tells the story of the a tribe arriving at the cave during the beginning of the movie over a 3D immersive backdrop of an early human encampment in the surrounding valley and continues to narrate the experience. Immediately following the introduction, a dream sequence illustrates different impressions of animals, alive during the time period, with ember particles to signify their importance to the residents of the cave. The next scene shows a couple of locations in the cave, prompting the player to illuminate the immediate surroundings with a handheld torch while elaborating on the highlighted cave paintings unveiled by the light. There are no direct locomotion methods available and the film changes locations automatically with a fade to black in between [40].

The second experience is a short guided tour of a virtual 3D scanned recreation of the real *Chauvet Cave* in which several cave paintings can be seen in great detail. Players are again led by a voiceover that explains the different motives and points out their location on the walls before being given an option to teleport to the next location. Remarkably the virtual environment depicts the real *Chauvet-Pont-d'Arc Cave* and not its visitor accessible real world replica *Grotte Chauvet 2* [40].

Relevance to this Thesis

The Dawn of Art is a recent example of the importance of VR SGs for cultural heritage and shows one of the many use-cases for the technology. The game allows players to explore an otherwise inaccessible cave in a highly detailed virtual 3D environment created from optical scans and provides guidance by means of voiceover audio. Additionally unique and engaging insight into the past is provided in an immersive and semi-interactive way, that is impossible outside of VR.

The methods applied in the game could be used in a similar manner to teach about UCH and environmental awareness in relation to the oceans. A number of important historical and cultural sites are located underwater, similarly inaccessible to untrained individuals, but potentially surveyable by professionals. Virtual recreations of such UCH locations implemented in a VR game offer the opportunity for a larger audience to engage with the history and raise interest in the field.

The lack of interactive capabilities however, could result in boredom over time and limits the replayability of the experience. The inclusion of proper gameplay and immersive interaction could facilitate more effective practical learning while also increasing its appeal and enjoyment.

3.2. DIVR

DIVR is a VR snorkeling system developed by *Ballast Technologies* for the use in resorts and waterparks. Their waterproof HMD technology enables visitors to immerse themselves in a virtual environment while physically located within real water. Five different experiences are available, ranging from different underwater locations to space and skydiving, though all related in some way to the feeling of weightlessness awarded by swimming in water. As the HMD blocks a users entire FOV, they are anchored to the ground with a tether and kept afloat with a buoyant, while breathing through a snorkel integrated into the setup. For further sensory stimulation the VR system can be extended with a haptic motor system, emitting variable thrusts of water towards the users, in the in *DIVR+* configuration [42]. An alternative product by the same company implements a waterproof HMD based VR System for the use in waterslides, allowing riders to experience similar virtual environments while descending [43].

Relevance to this Thesis

The *DIVR* system highlights the creative application of VR technology for the immersive simulation of diving by situating the entire experience in physical water. Despite not classifying as a SG due to its explicit focus on entertainment, the technology holds ample value for the use in education or training. The alignment of the virtual and physical environments when undergoing a virtual dive while floating in real water could increase both immersion and presence immensely and allows unique interaction that would be impossible in other

VR systems. Additionally *DIVR* seems to show positive results in the reduction of Visually Induced Motion Sickness (VIMS) [44], which further reinforces its potential for the use in immersive VR diving simulation.

One major downside of the system are the visual fidelity and tracking capabilities in comparison to other VR HMDs. Due to its waterproof nature, the *DIVR* HMD has to be self contained and runs entirely on mobile hardware, which is often considerably weaker than desktop tethered systems. Furthermore there is no support for hand tracking or input devices of any kind, which limits the possible experiences to non-interactive tours and makes the technology unfit for use in realistic training or practical education.

3.3. VISAS Project

The *Virtual and augmented exploitation of Submerged Archaeological Sites Project (VISAS Project)* is one of the most important related works to this paper. The project includes multiple papers directly relating to VR in use with underwater cultural heritage and diving. "VISAS is a collaborative research project aimed to improve the responsible and sustainable exploitation of underwater archaeological sites" [45]. The project aims to develop an "integrated package of services", some of which are intended to improve "the divers' experience in the underwater site", while others are made "to promote the induced tourist activity through the development of an innovative virtual tour of the site" [45]. While the main interest to this thesis is the development of the virtual tour, the *Virtual Dive Experience*, the methods and the architecture of the project in general have to be elaborated to understand the full impact of the project's research.

The Project shares its findings via an official website [45] and multiple papers and articles [46, 47, 48], though two [47, 48] are of particular interest, as they focus mostly on the 3D reconstruction efforts and the development of the *Virtual Dive Experience*.

Underwater Scans & 3D Reconstruction

The first goal of the *VISAS Project* was the authentic recreation of diving and underwater cultural heritage sites as 3D models, to use in further work in the project. To achieve this, a multi-step process 3.2 was enacted to acquire the needed data for accurate reconstruction in 3D. As a first step an initial inspection of the possible diving site is carried out and points of special interest are identified for more detailed further surveys. The entire area that is to be scanned, is then swept with Multibeam echosounders, that are "... usually employed for the generation of bathymetric maps in archaeological contexts ..." [49]. They "... allow for acquiring a great amount of data at long distances and in presence of bad visibility, but the results are affected by low resolution and do not contain color information" [49]. This survey is conducted by placing the high frequency multibeam equipment on a boat, from where data can be gathered up to a depth of one hundred meters, resulting in a low resolution

bathymetric map representing the seabed of the site [48].

To increase the level of detail for previously selected areas of interest, a secondary survey is conducted on only these spots, via optical systems, which "... in contrast, are more suited for close-range acquisitions and allow for gathering high-resolution, accurate 3D data and textures, but the results are strongly influenced by the visibility conditions" [49]. This secondary optical survey is carried out by divers with underwater cameras taking a large number of overlapping photographs of each individual spot. The images are enhanced using multiple methods to increase their chromatic quality for further processing. A 3D model is then created for each spot from the enhanced images using photogrammetry technology. [48].

Finally both optical and acoustic models need to be merged to form one complete 3D reconstruction of the entire diving site. The location, scaling, and orientation of both objects in relation of each other are performed using multiple techniques, most notably geolocation systems and direct measurements done by divers to increase accuracy. Merging is performed "[...] by means a selective fitting of the acoustic mesh along the contours shared with the optical mesh" [47], resulting in a multi-resolution mesh [47].

Textures are applied to the high-resolution areas of the mesh by blending and merging the previously taken images of it on the 3D mesh. The remaining low-resolution mesh is textured using standard tile-based texture mapping. The result is a highly accurate and realistic 3D model that can be used in further work. The collected data and reconstructed models are then saved to a database and made available to other services in the project through a web service software. [47].

Virtual Dive Experience

The Virtual Dive Experience created by the *VISAS Project* is a VR System designed to "provide instructions and information in a playful and educative manner..." [49]. It simulates a dive in one of two regions in South Italy, *Capo Colonna* and *Cala Minnola*, to allow non-divers to experience the underwater archaeological findings present there in a safe and playful, but realistic way. This is intended to promote diving tourism and increase the appeal of the area to tourists [48].

Hardware Setups

The Virtual Dive Experience was designed for two different VR Hardware setups, the immersive and semi-immersive experiences.

The semi-immersive setup consists of a full HD 3D monitor using passive 3D technology, for cost and convenience reasons. Players interact with it by means of a handheld tablet device. The 3D monitor provides the main viewport into the 3D virtual world of the experience, while touchscreen buttons on the tablet allow the player to move the camera and the virtual diver around. The tablet can also show multimedia content on its screen, when close to a

Figure 3.1.: Architecture of the integrated package of services proposed by the VISAS project.

Source: VISAS Website [45]

Figure 3.2.: Processing pipeline of acoustic and optical data.

Source: VISAS Website [45]

point of interest and an interaction button is selected [48].

The immersive setup uses a motion tracked head-mounted display to completely immerse the player into the virtual world. The HMD has two screens, one in each eye, which allow a natural 3D view into the experience, while isolating the player from the real world environment. Interaction can be performed by means of a single motion tracked controller, with which the camera of the virtual diver can be moved, while the viewing direction is controlled by the player's head movement (tracked through the HMD). When close to a point of interest, multimedia content about it can be shown in a 3D frame, when the controller's trigger is pressed [48].

Gameplay

The gameplay of the Virtual Dive Experience is largely the same on both the immersive and semi-immersive setup. Players can engage in the virtual 3D reconstruction of one of the two underwater archaeological sites and control a virtual diver on either a guided, or unguided,

free, tour of the area. After starting next to a boat on the surface, the game allows players to either freely explore the diving site themselves (free tour) or follow a virtual diver on a pre-routed tour of the site (guided tour). The movement controls are simple and allow for direct movement through the scene in the direction the controller is indicating [48]. Placed around the site are Point of Interest (POI) markers, which players can activate to receive additional multimedia information on the archaeological findings, flora, and fauna in the immediate vicinity. On the guided tour these markers are invisible until the virtual diving guide is close to them, resulting in an evolving story told through the right ordering of the content in the POIs, while they are always visible in the free tour [48].

Game Design

The *Virtual Dive Experience* "(...) has been developed according to the best practices related to the gamification design process (...) in order to maximize enjoyment and engagement through capturing the interest of learners (...)" [48]. The game consists of three different elements, exploration, interaction, and storytelling [48]. To facilitate exploration, the previously created 3D reconstruction is used as a base and extended with appropriate recreations of the coastline, a boat, and other objects, to create an realistic and immersive virtual world. The interaction is provided by the points of interest and the free movement through the scene, allowing players to actively engage with information on their own terms, instead of passively receiving the information [48]. Additionally the guided tour arranges the POIs in a specific order to create a story through the multimedia content accessible through interacting with them.

User Study

Following their chosen user-centered design process, the VISAS Project conducted a user study on the *Virtual Dive Experience* to involve player feedback into their design process. The study compared the user satisfaction and experience between users of the immersive and semi-immersive setup, focusing on subjective opinions, rather than objective data [48].

Participants were divided into four groups:

- Preteens (10 to 13 years old)
- Teenagers (14 to 16 years old)
- Male young adults (17 to 22 years old)
- Female young adults (17 to 24 years old)

After a demo of the system and testing both VR setups, participants were asked to fill out a questionnaire and answer questions. The study results show, that, while most participants have frequent experience with the multi-touch tablet of the semi-immersive setups, only a small number were familiar with the HMD technology of the immersive setup. However despite this unfamiliarity, all four groups reported a highly similar degree of usability, measured in 3 categories, learnability, system efficacy, and fun, between both

setups. Finally all four groups, indicated high subjective preference towards the immersive setup, despite being not as familiar with it, compared to the semi-immersive setup. The study concluded with the observation, that HMD technology was appropriate for the use-case at hand, especially when immersion and natural movement were of importance [48].

Augmented Diving

Parallel to the *Virtual Diving Experience*, the *VISAS Project* used the data that was gathered through scans and especially geopositioning technology in addition to the 3D reconstruction process 3.3 for the development of an augmented (reality) diving experience [49]. The *Augmented Diving Services* offer divers of one of the two previously mentioned underwater archaeological sites, the ability to view their position on a 3D map of their surroundings using a special underwater tablet. In addition the tablet also offers a guided underwater tour and information on points of interest to the real diver, in a similar way to how the *Virtual Dive Experience* provides these services to the player [49, 49]. However as this system is not directly related to the topic of this paper, it is only mentioned in passing, to highlight the diverse use-cases of the technology.

Relevance to this Thesis

As previously mentioned the *VISAS Project* is of high interest to this thesis. Not only does it develop a VR System similar to the one proposed in a later chapter of this thesis, including a user study on the usability and relevance of such a system, it also outlines an efficient pipeline for the 3D reconstruction of real world diving sites. We will also focus largely on the immersive setup outlined above, as it is the more relevant to this paper and the proposed design and prototype below. However the gameplay implemented in the *Virtual Dive Experience* is lacking when compared to many modern commercial VR game releases, SG, or simulators.

While it provides a very realistic digital environment, largely consisting of 3D reconstructions of the real underwater archaeological site, the act of diving itself is heavily simplified. While likely done as a conscious decision to keep the experience as simple as possible, implementing more complex mechanics such as air supply, buoyancy control devices, or currents, could help with immersion and introduce more elements of play to further enjoyment and possibly learning outcome [33]. The added realism could also lead to increased enthusiasm for diving as a recreational activity, potentially benefiting diving tourism in general. Introducing more opportunities for interaction, for example simplified tasks real divers would have to perform on an underwater archaeological excavation, or more complex interactions, could also increase the engagement players have with the virtual world.

The immersive VR setup does not take advantage of the full potential that modern VR Systems with motion tracked HMDs and controllers provide. The *VISAS Virtual Dive Experience* only utilises the head tracking to look around, while one of two possible controllers is used

for interaction and simple movement, wherein the player moves in the direction the controller is pointing. Independent tracking of both hands and the HMD with 6Degrees of Freedom (DoF) allows for a large amount of interaction possibilities as recent release of commercial VR games have shown. With VR becoming more common players become gain experience with the medium and may come to expect more engaging and complex interaction. New forms of movement in VR environments have evolved [50], for example hand gestures mimicking swimming motions translating directly to movement in VR [51, 52].

Lastly most information is delivered to the player via multimedia content displayed in a virtual 3D frame [48], forcing the player to stop his exploration of the immersive virtual world to focus on flat text or images. VR Systems and SG in general can offer less obtrusive and more engaging ways of conveying information through diegetic means, for example through voiceovers, dynamic scene highlights, or interactive 3D models [53].

4. Immersive Diving Simulation in VR

There have been countless attempts to simulate different activities and experiences in VR, to varying success. In this chapter we examine the intricacies of diving and discuss the methods that could be used to emulate the experience in VR. Existing technologies are analysed and their application in the creation of an immersive VR diving simulator considered.

4.1. The Role of Immersion, Realism, and Authenticity

In chapter 2 the importance of immersion for games and VR, as well as the factors influencing and interacting with immersion have been highlighted.

However, as we are trying to simulate a real world activity in VR, we also have to look at the quality of the simulation itself, how closely it is to the real world experience, and not just the quality of the virtual environment or overall experience. This can be expressed through the concepts of realism and authenticity. The level of realism describes how similar something is to the real world, often in regards to physics, looks, and behaviour, while the level of authenticity describes how genuine something is in relation to the original it is replicating. As a diving simulator attempts to simulate the real world, both terms are very similar in this context and can be used interchangeably.

To create an immersive and authentic diving simulation in VR both immersion and realism have to be considered, as both an unrealistic but immersive portrayal, or a realistic but boring game would fail to achieve our goal.

4.2. Visuals

One of the most important aspects in creating any realistic simulation of an activity in VR is the visual component. As humans rely heavily on their eyesight to experience the real world, a faithful and accurate virtual image is the foundation of any attempt to simulate a virtual reality. Surprisingly some studies have shown, that visual fidelity and realism do not have a strong influence on the feeling of presence and immersion, once a bare minimum visual representation is available [28]. However other studies [54, 31] conclude that visual realism and display fidelity could have an impact on certain visual tasks.

Visual quality and realism might be of increased importance for immersion if the simulation places an emphasis on the location the dive takes place in. In particular when a real world dive spot is supposed to be replicated in detail, be it for entertainment or archaeological use, visual realism and parity to the original is paramount. For a use-case that focuses more on

the mechanics than the environment of the dive, visual fidelity might not be as important.

Realistic visuals mostly depend on the quality of the assets used in the creation of the simulation. While high quality models and textures could be generated by artists, as is usual in the games industry, technologies like photogrammetry can be used to create highly realistic assets from pictures of real world objects and locations. For diving simulation specifically, bathymetric survey data could be employed in combination with photogrammetry and traditional asset creation for high visual realism and fidelity underwater environment [48]. This is particularly interesting for the authentic recreation of Caesarea Maritima further highlighted in Guy Kost's thesis [4].

In addition to the assets themselves, shaders and post-processing effects can be employed to further increase the visual fidelity. Realistic water refraction and other visual effects present in underwater environments can be simulated using physics based shaders and rendering systems [55].

4.3. Interaction

The importance of interaction to immersive dive simulation in VR is difficult to quantify. On one hand, interaction with the virtual environment is shown to increase immersion in VR, which can lead to a better simulation experience [30]. The degree of realism of the interaction on the other hand does not seem to have an influence on the level of immersion [2]. Furthermore, interaction based purely on realistic simulation might even cause confusion in players and lower their sense of embodiment in certain situations [56].

However we still have to assess the role of interaction in the context of the simulation itself. To simulate an activity in an authentic way, all, or at least a sufficiently large portion, of the aspects of the activity have to be simulated accurately. One important aspect of diving is the interaction with the world, be it the stir up of silt, or the change to the alternate air source, wherefore we think, that realistic interactions are a vital part of an immersive VR diving simulator.

To create realistic interactions with the world, the original interactions have to be studied in detail to be recreated authentically. As interactions can quickly grow in number, especially when combined, it is likely more efficient to have interaction behaviour emerge from a general system of rules, that governs everything instead of implementing each interaction by itself. This approach is time proven and can, for example, be found in the use of physics engines. This has been further elaborated below. For dive simulation specifically, it is important to recreate the function of the dive equipment realistically. A lot of the info needed for that can be found in the PADI *Open water diver manual* [57].

Most modern VR System use some kind of controller to facilitate the interaction [18], which often requires the abstraction of certain tasks to button presses. A more realistic approach might be to use hand and finger tracking and transfer them directly to the virtual world, allowing for a more natural and authentic way of interaction with the virtual world. However, one side, previously disregarded when examining interactions with a virtual world, is the feedback, that is provided back to the player. As this issue extends beyond the topic of interactions, it is further elaborated on in section 4.5.

4.4. Locomotion

One of the most fundamental types of interactions in VR is the movement through the virtual environment, often referred to as locomotion. Diving is largely comprised of movement, that is impossible outside of water, which poses a unique challenge when trying to simulate the activity.

While regular purely thumbstick or button based inputs could be used, motion tracking technology available in many modern VR systems [18] enables virtual locomotion, that requires physical movement in the real world, which has been linked to high levels of immersion and flow [58] and could be considered more authentic.

Swimming could be simulated by tracking players' hand/arm movements in relation to their body to register their arm strokes and convert them into virtual locomotion. Breaststrokes can easily be performed in a sitting or standing position and are ideal for diving as they work both underwater and at the surface. However, problems arise, when trying to simulate leg kicks, the primary method of locomotion underwater, which cannot be performed properly when standing or sitting and could require additional motion tracking.

This could be solved by physically situating the entire VR system inside real water, using technology similar to *DIVR* [42], allowing players to swim in real life to swim in the virtual environment. There are no conclusive studies on the immersion benefit of this method yet, but it does seem to have a positive effect onvection, the illusion of self motion, and can reduce Visually Induced Motion Sickness (VIMS) [44, 59]. The downside is, that the system requires a large body of water and a hardware system that can be used in and under water, which is infeasible for most use-cases.

Another option to free players' legs for proper movement is by suspending them in the air using a harness-support-system. This awards full range of motion in all extremities and players can perform breaststrokes as well as leg kicks, that can be translated to virtual movement using motion tracking. However, a user-study conducted on such a system has shown the satisfaction to be quite low, with the supports negatively impacting immersion and realism [60].

Finally, the influence of breathing on the buoyancy of divers has to be considered, when diving is to be authentically simulated in VR. Divers can increase their body volume and

buoyancy by breathing in or decrease it by breathing out. Though seemingly small, this form of vertical control seems to have a large impact in perceived realism of the simulation [60]. Breathing can be reliably measured using a gas flow sensor, which could be implemented using a modified second stage mouthpiece [60]. Microphones could also be used to estimate the volume of air currently in the player's lungs.

We conclude that simulating the locomotion of diving is difficult to recreate authentically in VR. While arm based swimming might be feasibly implemented using motion tracking, the inclusion of real world leg movement into the simulator seems unfavourable and might have to be emulated using traditional thumbstick based locomotion. Movement based locomotion in general can tire the players and reduce immersion in certain cases [58], whereas the inclusion of traditional controls as a selectable alternative should be considered. Additionally, buoyancy control through breathing could be used to boost immersion and realism.

4.5. Haptics

Haptics refers to the sensory information delivered by touch or the techniques used to fake such sensory information [61]. While there is few conclusive evidence on the impact of haptics on immersion or realism, the technology is still developing and could improve the fidelity of VR in the future [28, 62].

The feelings of wetness and increased resistance when submerged in water are some of the first haptic sensations that come to mind in relation to diving, and could provide an increase in realism when properly applied to a VR simulator. The previously mentioned *DIVR* system [42] uses real water to create the most realistic sense of submergence possible, which however comes with the aforementioned downsides.

Another way to simulate the feeling of wetness is through thermal and vibrotactile means. Cold temperature, especially in combination with matching visuals, has been shown to improve player experience when used to simulate water. Vibrotactile actuators also show promising results when used in conjunction with temperature and can be used to simulate splashes [63]. Thermal exchange pads could be placed on regions of the body sensitive to temperature change, like wrist and face, for increased effect [60].

Water resistance might be replicable using gyroscopes attached to the player's limbs, utilising the gyroscopic effect to create variable resistance [64]. Alternatively, resistance bands, harnesses, or exoskeleton actuator systems could in theory achieve a similar resistance effect.

Objects and surfaces in the real world have a distinct texture and feel when held, that is not present in most VR systems today. Some simulators might incorporate replicas of real world objects in their design to increase the immersion or realism [42], but this approach is difficult when the virtual environment changes significantly or features a large number of directly interactible objects. An immersive VR diving simulator could incorporate realistic replicas of diving equipment like the mouthpiece, or Buoyancy Control Device (BCD) vest. This might

increase immersion and realism by letting players interact with authentic objects, but also poses significant technical challenges, as interactions with the virtual environment have to be taken into account. In particular the perceived weight change of the cylinder when entering or exiting the water would require a complicated system to be dynamically adjustable during the simulation.

Haptic gloves might offer a dynamic solution in the future, but a short survey of currently available models showed, that they are likely too limited in their ability to create tactile feedback. Some models also require extensive external hardware, that is likely to reduce immersion more than it could improve it in a VR diving simulator [65, 66].

4.6. Kinesthesia

Kinesthesia is the sense of the position and orientation of the body derived from receptors in muscles and joints [67]. In VR it is relevant to the feeling of embodiment in the virtual environment, especially if no haptic feedback is present [68].

During a dive, a diver's body is usually in a horizontal position, except when ascending or descending, while most VR systems require a user to sit or stand. This mismatch might have a negative effect on the level of immersion and could feel unrealistic. Two systems showcased earlier in this chapter solve this problem by allowing the player to experience the simulation in a authentic horizontal position by having them float in water [42] or suspending them with a support system [60]. This could increase the feeling of embodiment by lining up the virtual body with the real player, but both systems also showed significant limitations earlier, with one even suffering from a decrease in immersion due to a unsatisfactory implementation [60].

Matching the virtual body correctly with the player's might not be required for an immersive and authentic experience though. Playtests have shown that players sometimes forget the position of limbs in the real world, when they are not in their VR FOV [56] and can misjudge the extend of their body in the virtual world [68]. Furthermore it is possible for players to accept virtual bodies as their own, despite a significant visuomotor mismatch [69].

Inverse Kinematics (IK) could be used to create a realistic simulation of a player's arms from low amounts of motion tracking data, potentially resulting in increased feelings of embodiment in situations where virtual and real body do match. On the downside the contrast between realistic virtual arms and wrongly displayed legs could cause a break in immersion [70].

Ultimately we think, that kinesthesia is an important sense, that can greatly influence a player's sense of embodiment in VR. However, under certain conditions, likely when levels of immersion are generally high due to other factors, it might be more beneficial to help players forget the discrepancy between their real and virtual body, than it is to align their real limbs with the simulation or the other way around.

4.7. Acoustics

The sense of hearing is perhaps the second most important when assessing our surroundings and helps us perceive things outside our FOV. In immersive VR environments high fidelity audio can increase perceived realism and lead to a more immersive experience [71, 2].

When examining the role of audio in the simulation of diving, the drastically different behaviour of sound in water compared to air has to be taken into account. Due to water having a similar density to human eardrums, humans can not perceive the direction of sound underwater. Audio perception is further disrupted by increased sound propagation and unfamiliar acoustic effects [72].

Despite this, realistic audio was shown to have positive effects in VR diving simulators and can have a significant impact on immersion [60]. Furthermore, specialised underwater sound propagation models could be employed to modify audio dynamically and increase audio fidelity and simulation realism [73].

4.8. Summary

The thorough analysis of diving conducted in this chapter revealed the complexity of the activity and the many difficulties that have to be overcome when attempting to create a realistic simulation of the sport. Diving provides a multitude of different stimuli of which many are hard to replicate reliably and without immense effort. But the discussion of different possible solutions to the encountered problems resulted in a small number of feasible options.

In particular, it was discovered that many of the technologies intended to simulate complicated sensory inputs, while increasing simulation realism, tend to cause a decrease in levels of immersion due to factors related to the technical implementation. Some of the most effective methods also require extensive and specialised hardware setups and cannot be easily combined with others or used outside of specific locations. Altogether, this results in a majority of the technologies being unfit for use in a VR simulation system, that aims to provide a realistic and immersive diving experience.

We conclude that instead of using a large amount of technologies to simulate as many sensations present in diving as possible, the focus should be put onto creating a highly immersive experience using traditional VR technologies (e.g. HMDs, motion tracked controllers, etc.), increasing realism through authentic visuals, sounds, and interactions within those limitations. If built in a modular and extensible way, select additional technologies can be added for a more realistic sensory experience, but only if immersion is not lowered in the process. Remaining discrepancies with the real world are then likely to be far less noticeable. The result is a highly immersive VR system that can realistically simulate diving to a sufficient degree without dependence on certain locations or circumstances. The concrete design of such a system is the topic of the following chapter.

5. Design of a Virtual Reality Diving Simulator

In this chapter we want to propose a design for a highly modular VR System for an immersive diving simulator and two of its main use-cases. The design is based upon our own experiences with VR software and serious games, lesson learned from previous designs and systems in industry and academia [48, 74, 75], as well as modern guidelines for software engineering [76] and serious games [77, 78, 79, 53].

As modularity is one of the fundamentals of the design, in this paper we will initially focus on the different aspects and technologies needed for an underlying system that can be used to create different VR SG pertaining to the field of diving. Afterwards two designs for concrete VR experiences possible within the system will be proposed. A deeper look into the first proposed experience as serious game and how it furthers education as well as the mechanisms by which learning is facilitated in the player can be found in Guy Kost's "Examination of the role of Game Mechanics in Serious Games via analysis of an underwater archaeology simulation VR serious game" thesis, with which this paper was written in tandem [4].

5.1. Underlying System

At first the desired possibilities of the underlying VR System are presented, to outline a detailed goal for the design and the resulting simulators capabilities. This will be used throughout the chapter to build a design, that satisfies the required functionality. Several hardware and software configurations, based on VR Systems already in use today, were compared to each other and ultimately final candidates were chosen as best fit for the system. Finally the modular nature of the system will be further elaborated on, before proposing the individual modules that make up the various configurations possible with the final design.

5.2. Goal

The main goal of the system is to authentically simulate the entire act of diving to varying degrees of realism and interactivity using VR technology. It should allow for a wide variety of possible use-cases pertaining to the field of diving. On one hand, it must accommodate experienced divers, or individuals wanting to become one, by offering a realistic simulation of the sport with a high degree of intractability to allow for training and learning. On the other hand the system must also be able to provide support for immersive, low interaction

and low realism scenarios like virtual underwater tours in museum exhibits.

It is of note that the term realism, as used in this chapter, refers to the realism of the interactions or game mechanics and to a wider extent to the realism of the simulation. It does however not, unless specifically stated otherwise, refer to the realism of the graphics or the artstyle. While graphics and overall simulation realism are linked to a certain degree, the visual fidelity and artstyle are largely dependent on the assets generated outside of the VR simulation system and we have thus decided to exclude them altogether in the considerations of modularity and variability of realism. Graphics are of course still an important part of a simulation system, and will be variable, but largely independent of the degree of (simulation) realism. In the following, the realism and quality of graphics will be referred to as visual or graphical fidelity. For the same reasons, the level of realism of the audio utilised in the simulator is independent of the aforementioned realism of the simulation. It is referred to as audio fidelity in the following. The exception being realism when referring to the physics simulation of audio propagation, filtering, etc., which is referred to as acoustic fidelity.

In essence, the system should be able to adjust the degree of realism and the degree of interactivity independently of each other to support a large variety of diverse use-cases and resulting gameplays. For example, in the case of beginner dive training a high realism but low interactivity scenario might be required.

Figure 5.1.: Theoretical system use-cases in relation to level of realism and level of interactivity.

The system also needs to support fluid adjustments between levels on both the realism and

interactivity axis during compile time as well as runtime. This is to allow dynamic changes that might be required for certain use-cases, for example the gradual increase in difficulty during a simulated dive training lesson.

The system needs a hardware setup that enables a high degree of immersion, while being versatile enough to allow for the different configurations to support the many different intended use-cases. A high realism and interactability configuration could offer support modified real world diving equipment and high fidelity haptic feedback for temperature or wetness. Configurations intended for lower interaction need to be able to work entirely using simple and easy to understand control devices.

5.3. Design Philosophy

As a foundation for the design, an underlying design philosophy has to be set to enforce consistency throughout. Based on the desired functionalities of the VR System presented above in section 5.2, two main pillars of the design have been extracted.

5.3.1. Modularity

Modularity refers to the practice of grouping closely related parts of a system together to form an independent module. The inner workings of that module is then hidden away following the principles of information hiding and abstraction and the functionality of that module can be accessed by other modules and services through an interface [76]. This results in a number of benefits:

Critical data and functionality is contained within a module and not accessible from the outside, unless specifically offered via interfaces, which greatly increases data security and reduces the possibility of misuse. As modules are independent of each other, they can be easily exchanged or modified internally without compromising the functionality of other modules, provided the interfaces remain functional. A modular design can reduce costs by reducing or eliminating the duplication of functionality and thus reducing the amount of work needed. Modularity helps with reducing the complexity of a system, by grouping related subsystems into easier to understand modules, requiring designers and programmers to have in depth knowledge of the module they work on and the interface functionality of other modules, without knowing other modules intricacies.

We deemed a modular design especially valuable for the proposed VR diving simulator as it is supposed to allow for a large variety of different use-cases, which often require different functionalities. The decomposition of the system into modules would allow for easier addition of needed features, as well as the omission of the others.

5.3.2. Variability

The principle of Variability refers to the reliance of the functionality, provided by each module, on internal variables. Those variables are changeable at initial configuration of the system or live, during runtime. Each variable affects a certain part of the functionality, and a change in a variable prompts a change in the related part of the functionality. This is useful insofar, as that together with a modular design, it allows for even more variation in the provided functionality, in turn making a more diverse set of use-cases possible. Additionally, it allows for quicker testing, prototyping and easier integration of new modules.

5.4. Hardware Configuration

A number of different hardware systems and devices have to be considered, when choosing the hardware configuration for the VR diving simulator. In this section, we highlight three different hardware configurations, elaborate their positives and negatives for the use-case at hand, and ultimately choose one as the final candidate. Since a VR System is made up of multiple subsystems, as explained in chapter 2, a configuration is a combination of (sub-)systems into a new system, or setup.

5.4.1. Personal Computer

One of the most common hardware configurations that can be used for VR Systems is a typical consumer PC consisting of any common desktop computer, one or more displays, a mouse and keyboard, as well as optional input and output devices. Their advantage is their status as one of the most commonly targeted platform for commercial entertainment videogames resulting in general familiarity of users with the configuration [80].

However, the configuration only offers a low degree of possible immersion and presence due to desktop monitors usually only offering 2D images (3D is sometimes possible) in a small subsection of a users Field of View (FOV). Multiple monitors could be used to increase immersion, but the overall degree will still be lower compared to other methods highlighted further below [23].

Mouse and keyboard are common devices for interacting with virtual experiences, widely supported by existing hardware, and are easy to understand and employ for most users. While they are one of the standard interaction devices used in entertainment virtual environments, mouse and keyboard are unfit for proving complex and natural interaction for immersive VR Systems [23].

All in all, a normal desktop computer with monitor and mouse and keyboard input is not well suited for the VR diving simulation system outlined in this chapter, as it does not allow for the required realism and natural interaction. The low FOV further limits the configuration in its effectiveness due to limit it could put on possible levels of immersion.

5.4.2. CAVE

Another approach would be a hardware configuration based on a Cave Automatic Virtual Environment (CAVE). In a CAVE the player is surrounded on all sides, the ceiling, and the floor by surfaces displaying images, to form an 360 degree view of a virtual environment. The displaying of images can be achieved via projectors located outside of the main chamber, like the prototype in the original design, large screens used as the walls of the main chamber, or a mixture of both. The players head and eye position is tracked to allow for proper stereoscopic projection by adjusting the projected images [24].

The advantage of this system is the large degree of immersion as a result of the system allowing for full coverage of the user's FOV, as well as full body presence withing the system. In theory, it also facilitates direct player-to-player interaction within the same setup. This however requires the system to track both players independently of each other and display two different, individual stereoscopic projections to each player on the same display sides, which might not be possible in every CAVE device.

Diminishing the usefulness of this configuration is its size, low ease-of-setup, and low commercial availability to the general consumer. A CAVE system generally needs the same amount of space in the real world, as there is directly interactable space in the virtual world. In addition to that, most CAVEs need additional space on some sides for projection technology or other hardware [24]. Due to their size and complexity, they will likely require extensive setup, which takes time and expertise. While this might not be a problem for permanent installations, as appropriate for museums or industrial training facilities, it is unfit for more casual users, who might want to use the system in a general purpose room in their house, but can not afford the loss of a room for a permanent setup.

Lastly we think, CAVEs might prove difficult to generate an immersive underwater experience with altogether. When simulating a dive, specific effects like air bubbles or fogging goggles happen very close to the player themself, which might be hard to achieve believably in CAVEs, due to the screens being situated further away from the player. Additionally, all objects and gear players interact within the simulation would have to be present in the real world setup with them. Though great for haptic feedback, the missing weight reduction that occurs in real water due to buoyancy would result in a cumbersome and ultimately unimmersive experience. Some of these drawbacks could be mitigated by building special prop objects and gear directly designed for the VR System, however this would again increase cost and decrease ease-of-setup.

5.4.3. VR HMD System

The last configuration presented here is a combination of a modern VR HMD, an accompanying motion tracking system, two tracked controllers, and a processing unit. As outlined in chapter 2, there are a multitude of different VR headsets with different feature sets and

capabilities.

The HMD in this configuration is part of a modern VR hardware system (*Valve Index*, *HTC Vive*, etc.), consisting of the HMD itself, the aforementioned controllers, and a motion tracking system, either included in the headset itself (inside-out tracking), or as an external system (outside-in tracking) [18]. Both HMD and controllers need to be trackable with 6DoF to support the precise interaction that is necessary for a simulator system. In addition, the controllers need to allow for tracking entirely independent of the position and orientation of the headset (some HMDs do not support this [81, 18]). The processing unit is responsible for performing the calculations required to run the simulation and can take the form of an external desktop computer (Desktop VR), or be included in the headset itself (Standalone).

HMD based VR offers a high degree of immersion, similar to CAVEs [25], sometimes even surpassing them in certain metrics [82, 83]. When in use, HMDs have similar space requirements to a CAVE, but can also often dynamically change their playspace dimensions to allow for varied setups. For storage, they can be disconnected and taken apart to fit in small form factor cases or storage areas, ultimately offering a decisively smaller footprint [82]. Additionally, they are usually cheaper and more easily available on the consumer market [80].

The downsides of HMD based setups are, that they do not commonly allow for natural interaction with real objects, relying instead on controllers to influence virtual object, and their obstruction of view on the player's body, which can decrease immersion. Multi-user interaction is also only possible through the use of virtual avatars, which can feel unnatural to some players [82].

5.4.4. Conclusion

After a thorough comparison of all three hardware configurations and considerations on their positives and negatives, we elected to use a VR HMD system configuration as the base for our design. HMDs offer a high level of immersion in general and allow for the authentic simulation of a virtual environment. They provide an easy to setup, small form-factor, and affordable solution, that is already widely available to consumers and companies alike. The controllers, which after often bundled with the device, provide a sufficient way of interacting with the virtual environment and can be used to accurately track the users hand positions for other uses.

Many of their downsides can be mitigated to some degree through additional hardware or software. Haptic gloves and vests are in development to increase the level of realism in interactions with objects, improved controller design do not require constant holding, and camera based, controller-less hand tracking is also available in certain headsets [66, 84, 85]. Through the use of inverse kinematics or additional tracked markers, highly realistic virtual bodies can be created as a stand in for a players obstructed view of themselves, which has shown to increase perceived presence in the virtual world and could lead to better multi-user

Comparison of Hardware Configurations			
Category	Personal Computer	CAVE	VR HMD
Immersion	Low	High	High
Space Requirement	Desk	Roomsize	Size of User/Roomsize
Ease-Of-Setup	Easy	Hard	Medium
Cost	Low	High	Medium
Virtual Objects	Yes	No	Yes

Figure 5.2.: Simplified comparison of proposed hardware configurations based on section 5.4

interactions [86, 70]. Advances in lens, screen, and eye tracking technology are expected to reduce the screen door effect further and thus increase immersion [87]. Through use of pulley systems, wireless tethers, or entirely standalone HMDs, the movement restrictions could also be reduced [88, 81]. Specifically relevant to the subject of dive simulation is the fact, that added hardware such as body harnesses, scent dispensers, wetness simulators, etc. can be positioned close to the player without interrupting the view into the virtual world [60, 63].

Finally, it is important to add that a CAVE setup does not allow players to directly interact naturally with objects as if they were actually in an underwater environment, since objects brought into the CAVE would not behave like submerged in water, but rather as they do in air. In an HMD all things the player can interact with are entirely virtual and thus can be made to behave however we want.

5.5. Modules

Modules are the parts of the system that provide all functionality. Each module is independent and responsible for supplying certain services to the system and can be interacted with using an interface. A module's functionality can be influenced by settings changeable via variables provided by the module.

5.5.1. Core Module

The Core Module is the most central module in the system, providing core functionality that a lot of other modules depend on. While usually modules are composed of functionalities that pertain to the same overall feature, the Core Module is an outlier insofar, as it combines a larger number of not directly related functionalities. Most of the functionality offered by this module is usually performed by a game engine.

Realtime Rendering Pipeline

To transform the abstract data of assets and terrain into authentic images for use in a VR System, a realtime rendering pipeline is required. It is very important for this pipeline to offer native support for VR HMDs as otherwise visual artifacts could corrupt the experience. Both *Unreal Engine* and *Unity* offer this support and one of these two engines is a likely candidate for the proposed design [89, 90, 91].

Physics Back End

While explicit physics behaviour is largely implemented in the individual modules, a back end has to be present for all of them to work together. This back end has to be highly optimised for performance as many aspects of dive simulation require frequent physics calculations. Other models communicate with the back end to access global physics variables, check collisions, and prompt movement in objects controlled by physics.

Input Output Management

There are a multitude of VR HMDs currently available on the consumer market, most using unique hardware with varied capabilities [18]. To support as many devices as possible, a strong communication layer is required that unifies inputs, while individualising the unified output for each device.

The module also handles communication with custom hardware and outside software systems to facilitate extensions of the system in the future. The potential of specialised hardware to simulate sensory information, discussed in chapter 4, could be beneficial for future iterations of the simulator and therefore has to be included already in the design considerations before concrete plans of inclusion are made.

Development Editor

The proposed VR diving simulation system is based on the principles of modularity and variability, designed to support a large variety of use-cases and game types. A potent and easy-to-use development editor improves the speed of creating new content and allows in depth customisation of the experience. It is the main user interface for developers and is used to setup anything within the system. Environments are created here, assets imported, models implemented and configured with a specialised mode allowing editing in VR itself for a improved sense of scale and faster testing [92]. A reduced version is also offered to certain users of the system to allow for limited customisation of the system without the help of the core development team.

5.5.2. Water Simulation Module

Diving is an activity that can only be performed in and under water, wherefore a solid and extensible water simulation system is essential to the system as a whole. The system needs to

support water simulation on multiple levels and is one of the base modules, that will almost always be present in any system configuration.

There are two main aspects of water simulation, the graphical component, that creates authentic visuals for the player to see, and the physics component that governs the realistic behaviour of objects interacting with and in water. Both components work hand in hand to create high fidelity simulations for bodies of water that the player can explore in VR. As per our design philosophy, it is vital for the entire module's functionality to be fully customisable using internal variables and allow for modular extension using interfaces. General features include adjustable waves based on spectra, configurable current zones, and realistic blending of areas with different parameters. This way common situations including tides, storms, maelstroms, and shore waves can be easily constructed and dynamically changed before or at runtime.

Bodies of water created with the module offer high graphical fidelity using the physics parameters of the simulation to present realistic visuals to the players, which can potentially lead to higher immersion and a more authentic experience in the simulation, as discussed in the previous chapter. The colour and light interaction of the water is highly adjustable using different maps to replicate real life physical phenomena like refraction, subsurface scattering, etc. When interacting with larger dynamic objects or static environmental geometry, foam is rendered on top of the waves and influenced by the wave movement. Most importantly the module supports extensive underwater visuals in VR, that can be seamlessly transitioned into by moving under the water surface. Different visual conditions can be created by editing the aforementioned variables, allowing for crystal clear tropical reef explorations and murky lake excavations to be presented in the same game.

The underlying physical calculations of the module provide the basic functionality for both the authentic visuals and the interactions with other modules. Bodies of water are simulated based on variables that relate to real world water physics and enable intuitive configuration with realistic values. The simulation calculates the resulting behaviour at runtime in cooperation with the physics back end from the core module and passes them on internally for the visual representation of water. Other modules can query or change this data to calculate their own behaviour or influence other connected systems dynamically.

In addition to simulation realism and visual fidelity, the system needs to run smooth and has to be optimised for performance. VR HMD rendering itself is highly resource intensive due to two different images being rendered every frame for the stereoscopic view, requiring systems targeting the platform to be particularly performance optimised. Level of Detail, Culling, and similar techniques could provide the performance increase needed for the system to work in even more complicated virtual scenes [55].

5.5.3. Player Controller Module

The Player Controller Module provides all functionality directly related to the avatar, through which the player interacts with the world from a first person perspective. The player avatar is a special object in the virtual environment. While it should obey general physical constraints and systems presented in the virtual environment, the player's inputs should sometimes take priority, and in certain cases overrides for functionalities provided by other modules need to be created to ensure a smooth experience for the player which minimises the risk of VIMS [93].

Player Camera

The player camera provides the main viewport into the virtual environment. It allows the player to see the world, terrain, and objects, read heads up display text, etc from a first person perspective. The camera's field of view is adjusted to the specific field of view supported by the currently connected VR HMD, which is queried via the Core Module. Post-processing effects can be applied to the camera by other modules via the interface.

Head Movement

The raw HMD tracking data provided by the Core Module is applied to the player avatars head, within which the player camera is located. By moving their head in real life, a player can move the player avatars head accordingly. This allows players to look around the virtual environment in a natural way and perform limited movement like ducking. Additionally, the position of the ground and headset can be used to calculate the players height.

Hand Movement

Similar to the head movement, the raw tracking data from the handheld controllers are provided by the Core Module to the Player Controller Module, where they are applied to the hands of the player avatar. This allows the player to move each hand independently of each other, and the head in 6 degrees of freedom. Certain buttons on the controller correspond to certain animations on the hand model of the avatar, for example pressing the trigger will move the virtual index finger into a curled position. Additionally, finger tracking could be implemented through an external module based on the player controller, to give more control over gestures and enable hand signs, as often used in diving for communication [57]. However, finger tracking support is not available in all VR HMD configurations and is therefore not included as a default feature [18].

Player Physics

While other modules might already provide a general physics system, we decided on treating the player avatar as a special case in the physics simulation. Real time physics engines can sometimes destabilise leading to large forces or other errors, possibly causing the player avatar

to be moved rapidly without intention, which is one of the causes for motion sickness [93]. The player avatar's collision differentiates between the hands and the rest of the body, with the former colliding with many items and terrain, while the latter usually only allows for collision with terrain or larger objects. This could also help with a better feeling of presence, as players expect to fit into tighter spaces than the default character collision might allow for [68]. Additionally the player locomotion is heavily tied to the simulation physics to allow for realistic motion, making it easier to implement when player physics is handled in the same module.

Specifically player buoyancy is handled by the Player Controller, as it has to be more precisely calculated than general object buoyancy, to allow for more intricate control. Buoyant forces applied to the player avatar are heavily dependent on multiple variables provided by the player controller itself and other modules interacting with the player (i.e interactive objects), some of which can be changed during a virtual dive. Buoyancy calculation was a major focus in prototype development and the exact methodology used is explained in section 6.5.1.

Player Locomotion

To support a robust realistic diving simulation, the player must be able to traverse different environments, especially walking on solid ground, swimming on the surface of a body of water, and diving underwater. The Player Controller module dynamically decides on the locomotion type, that is being used based on the environment it is currently situated in, which is queried from other modules. Additionally to raise comfort for different users, and reduce the possibility of VIMS, different versions of locomotion should be offered for each environment available [94, 58, 50].

Ground Locomotion

When the player avatar is on solid ground and not sufficiently submerged in water, the ground locomotion is to be chosen as the active locomotion for the player. After consolidation of previous research into VR based locomotion [94, 58, 50] and contemporary consumer VR games[52, 74], three different types have been decided upon:

As the default ground locomotion type, we selected **controller based continuous locomotion**. By using the thumbstick (or any similar bi-axial analogue input device) on the left controller the player can control their movement in any direction in a similar fashion to other video games. The up/forward direction of the thumbstick corresponds either to the direction the player is viewing (head-oriented) or the direction their left hand is pointing to (hand-based). This movement type has proved to be immersive and easy to use, allowing players to focus on the other aspects of the game instead of having to focus on the movement itself [58, 50]. One downside of this movement type is, that a certain percentage of players experience motion-sickness when first using the technique, before they adjust after a short

time [58].

The second locomotion type is **controller based instant teleportation** and was chosen as an alternative to the aforementioned controller based continuous locomotion, as the former is less likely to cause motion-sickness in players [58, 77]. The player can activate the teleport mode by pressing and holding a button on the left controller. In teleport mode a ballistically downward curved beam is emitted from the player's left hand, ending in a circular teleport marker where it collides the ground. The marker shows the player where they will be teleported to and turns red when an invalid destination is selected. When the held button is let go, the player avatar is instantly transported to the location the marker indicates, allowing the player to move to any valid place in range. While generally a fast and easy to use method of locomotion, due to the instant nature of the teleportation, the movement type can feel less immersive and could cause eyestrain in certain users [58]. Some commercial VR games attempt to mitigate this effect with temporary decreasing FOV or an artificial "blinking" [52, 74].

The last available locomotion type is **controller based continuous rapid shifting**. In essence very similar to the controller based instant teleportation, it uses the same activation scheme and UI. The difference is, that instead of an instant teleport, the player is continuously moved to the selected destination rapidly, in less than 300ms [95]. This locomotion was derived from promising results in node based locomotion [95] combined with the previous teleport locomotion for dynamic node placement. While not subject to extensive academic research yet, this locomotion technique was used in the commercial released VR game *Half-Life: Alyx*, in which playtesters reported an increased sense of immersion due to better experiencing the traversed space [68].

Swimming Locomotion

At the beginning and the end of a dive simulation, it is likely that the player will have to spend time at the surface of the water floating or swimming. While swimming and diving are generally part of the same overall movement set, we decided to treat swimming at the surface as a special case to increase the comfort of the simulation. During swimming (as opposed to diving), the player's vertical movement is dampened, allowing them to keep their head over the water more easily. To sink back down a decisive action, like a stronger downward movement input, or the reduction of buoyancy using a Buoyancy Control Device (BCD). Depending on the chosen settings within the module, the swimming mode is activated when one, or a combination of the following cases is present:

- The player is under a certain depth.
- The player's buoyancy is over a certain threshold (usually related to the BCDs inflation).
- The player's submergence is under a certain threshold.

The first swimming locomotion type is **motion based natural swimming**. Using this method, the player has to move their arms in front to back breaststroke to propel themselves in their intended direction. Intended as a realistic movement type, we hope that the arm movement helps the player immerse themselves in the virtual environment in a similar way to how walking-in-place movement was perceived as more realistic by some [58]. The movement is detected using the motion tracked controllers, and the swimming movement vector is calculated from the movement of both controllers. To avoid back to front hand movement during the recovery of a breaststroke registering as a backwards swimming motion, the hand movement is only applied as movement in certain valid conditions. The player's hands need to be extended fully in front or side of their body and their hands must be turned upside down and backwards as if forming a shovel for the water. In the same way, an intended valid backwards movement can be performed by executing the hand movement in the opposite direction, this time turning the hands right side up again, while still performing the movement with extended arms. To bring the hands back (or forth) without triggering movement, the player can slowly extend or retract their arms in a straight line in front of their chest. Alternatively or in addition, pressing both trigger buttons can be added as a requirement to count as a valid stroke, which could help to reduce unwanted movement.

The second swimming locomotion type is **controller based pointing**. This technique is intended as a low realism but higher convenience movement type, to make swimming more accessible to all kinds of players. To move using this technique, the player has to point their left controller in the direction they want to move, and squeeze the trigger button. Should the controller have an analogue trigger button, the swim speed is proportional to the degree to which the button is pressed. The use of a thumbstick for moving in swimming has purposefully been decided against, as mapping the two thumbstick axis to the 3 dimensional movement of swimming could result in confusion.

Diving Locomotion

Diving will likely make up the majority of the time spent in a diving simulator, so a robust and realistic underwater movement set is essential for a diving simulation system. As we discussed in chapter 4, during a real dive the vertical movement under water is mostly performed using the BCD and buoyancy control using breathing, while vertical movement is done using leg kicks and rarely arm movement.

To support such a complex movement, we came up with a movement system called **immersive hybrid diving**. After transitioning out of swimming into a fully submerged state, the player now has multiple options of moving at the same time. The regular breast stroke motion based natural swimming motion is still available to the player at any depth, however the dampening to the vertical movement is removed. As we failed to realistically emulate leg kicks while standing and without additional tracking hardware, we decided on a controller based approach to horizontal movement. When the player places their hands in an area close to their abdomen, in a similar way to real divers, pressing the trigger on the left controller

propels the player in the direction they are looking, omitting the vertical vector of the movement entirely, resulting in planar movement. The speed is hereby either set or controlled by the strength of the trigger press, if an analogue trigger is present on the controller. Smaller vertical movements can be made by holding down an additional button on the left controller in addition to the trigger to include the vertical movement with some dampening.

As an alternative, the player can again use the **controller based pointing locomotion** type, which behaves similar to its swimming counterpart by allowing them to move in the direction their controller is pointing, with dampening applied to all vertical movement. This is again included as a less immersive option to increase comfort for certain players who might prefer less arm movement. For diving, this movement type can be used in conjunction with the leg kick emulation from the previous paragraph.

For larger depth changes, for example on ascend or descend, players have to use the BCD, inflating it to ascend, or deflating it to descend. This can be done using the Low Pressure Inflator (LPI) usually located on the left side of the chest. When held, the upper button on the holding controller corresponds to inflating, while the lower button corresponds to deflating the BCD. The ascension/descension is then handled by the player physics system based on the increase/decrease in volume.

Player Avatar Inverse Kinematics

To increase the immersion and feeling of embodiment in the player when in the simulation, we decided upon including an option for a first person visible, fully modelled and animated player avatar body in the design. An accurate visual representation of the player's virtual body can help them understand their location and orientation in the original space, allowing players to better interact with the virtual environment and potentially avoid misunderstandings [70].

The chosen hardware configuration only tracks the head and both controllers, which can be used to approximate the position of the arms, elbows and upper body and to an extent the lower body and legs using an Inverse Kinematics (IK) solver [86, 70]. The upper body animations are completely dynamic and calculated using IK for the most realistic virtual representation of arm and hand positions as well as torso orientation. As there is no leg tracking in the default configuration the legs have to rely on a mix of traditional animation and approximations provided by the IK solver. During the use of walking locomotion, the lower body is animated using state based animations using IK to place feet correctly on the floor and adjust the orientation based on arm and head orientation [86]. While swimming or diving locomotion are active, a state based animation influenced by the player's swimspeed and direction is used for the lower body, while IK calculates the right orientation.

5.5.4. Interactive Object Module

Interactive objects are objects that interact with the player, other objects, or the environment in any way. Most have their own custom behaviour implemented by this module or a sub-module that offers additional functionalities. The interactive object module offers a number of base features, like buoyancy calculations, basic collisions, the option to be picked up, etc., that other features can be built upon. Section 6.6 provides some examples of objects implemented in the prototype based on the module proposed here.

The player interacts with the virtual environment mainly through various interactive objects, to facilitate a realistic and engaging experience. UIs are realised through objects where possible, as they allow for intuitive and diegetic interaction that could exist in a similar way in reality, instead of purely fictional classic UI elements seen often in games. Animations within the objects react dynamically to input instead of playing fixed movements as players often want to interact with analogue interfaces directly. Some interactive objects can be picked up by physically reaching out to them using the motion tracked controllers and stored in their inventory or let go again elsewhere. When held in hand, objects can add functionality to certain inputs or even influence features provided by other modules. To reduce frustration and offer a less exhausting method of grabbing, an optional alternate system is in place that transports objects into the player's hand when pointing at one and activating the grab input [53].

5.5.5. Asset Data Import Module

In chapter 4 it was discussed that authentic high fidelity assets are one possible way to increase the perceived realism of the virtual environment. One of the projects highlighted in chapter 3 [48] also demonstrated the viability of high quality realistic asset creation from detailed scans of real UCH sites.

The proposed module acts as the last step of a multipurpose asset creation and import pipeline, that enables the easy conversion of real world underwater survey data to in-system assets. Primarily two different data types would be supported, bathymetric pointclouds and photogrammetry data. The high pointclouds are created during bathymetric survey, which is used to quickly generate accurate topological data of the seabed and objects located there using acoustic beams. Photogrammetry data is obtained by taking a large number of images from all sides of an object or area using an underwater camera. These pictures are then colour-corrected, analysed, and stitched together using commercially available photogrammetry software generating a high fidelity pointcloud and textures. Supplied with both datasets the module merges optical and acoustical pointclouds to one multi-resolution mesh and applies the textures generated from the images to the appropriate spots. A tile based texturing approach is utilised to fill the remain untextured areas of the mesh with generic ocean floor textures appropriate for the region, smoothly blending them with the photogrammetry textures [46, 47, 96].

5.6. Experience Design

In addition to the more technical description of the VR System proposed in the previous sections, we designed one possible implementation of the system as a serious game. The description here is only a summary with the subject examined in further depth and from a disparate scientific perspective in Guy Kost's thesis [4].

5.6.1. Overview

The proposed serious game is an immersive diving simulator aimed at the general consumer market as a ludo-educative experience and to museum (or other) exhibits, using a specialised version, to improve awareness for UCH and spark interest in the diving sport. The player can embark on virtual free-form dives with realistic equipment in recreations of real underwater archaeological dive sites to learn about the day to day work of divers and archaeologists. In addition to UCH focused experiences and education, the game also serves as a platform to teach the basics of PADI compliant diving and aims to prepare people for real world dive training.

5.6.2. Gameplay

The gameplay of the experience is structured in multiple stages, loosely oriented on the stages of training of a real diver and underwater archaeologist [97].

For a consumer release on platforms like Steam or itch.io, the stages and levels are sequentially unlockable in a story mode configuration. Each new stage and level increases in difficulty and complexity to keep players engaged and entertained. This is achieved by gradually changing variables in the systems modules and activating new modules once their functionality is required.

For an exhibit, a small subsection of singular levels can be chosen or even new ones created based on the theme of the exhibit. The difficulty is also adjusted down using the variables and modules to create a less realistic and interactive simulation, but allow for ease of use for inexperienced players.

5.6.3. Tutorial Stage

The tutorial stage (and the entire experience to a certain point) is designed to introduce players gradually into the diving sport and slowly building the up to a first virtual open water dive without an instructor. The learning curve is intentionally set to gradually introduce new information and tasks one at a time to never overwhelm players and give them enough time to process and understand [79]. Shortcuts and fast-forwarding opportunities are provided for experienced or fast learning players to not lose their engagement, while also providing the option to repeat any given lesson or exercise to further deepen the knowledge gained [79, 78]. The training is modelled after the PADI Open water diver manual and the PADI Open Water Diver course [57, 97].

After a short optional tutorial explaining the basics of the VR system itself, the controller and button mapping, the comfort options, and available movement types, the player starts their virtual dive training in a virtual dive center. The center is a large modern (partially futuristic) building with separate spaces and stations for the different aspects of dive training, providing players a realistic and believable environment, which is important to properly engage players with the material [79].

A NPC dive instructor guides them through the stations, offering explanations for the tasks or information at hand, testing the player on their knowledge afterwards in either multiple choice tests (the main PADI testing form [57]) or practical demonstrations. The instructor provides detailed feedback, helping players understand their mistakes and inform them of their progress [78]. This split in three different phases is an effective method of facilitating learning tasks and supports players throughout the process [79].

Theoretical content is present in varied ways using text, voiceovers, and, where applicable, interactive content (i.e using a handheld balloon to demonstrate air compression at depth) to allow players to experience the information in different forms and apply it shortly after [79, 78].

Practical content and practice dives (in pool and ocean) follow the same principle of guided experiential learning, utilising the immersive VR technology to realistically simulate the tasks at hand and allow the player to naturally interact with the world and equipment to solve problems and collaborate with the NPC dive instructor and buddy [79, 78].

At the end of the training phase the player has to complete a multiple choice test, proving their knowledge of the theory learned throughout and a final virtual practice dive to demonstrate their practical skills. A final feedback is presented to the player and they are allowed to progress into the free-form dive stage.

5.6.4. Free-form Dive Stage

In the free-form dive stage of the game, the player is awarded more freedoms to explore and learn on their own, instead of the more focused approach used in the tutorial stage. The story has the player join a team of archaeological divers on a modern research vessel, travelling the world, partaking in varied virtual underwater excavations inspired by, or modelled after real world UCH sites. This serves as a backdrop to allow for a variety of different locations and the different challenges and activities that come with it, providing players with choices to choose from, reducing the chances of boredom and furthering the learning goals [79]. This is supported by the system's modular structure and reliance on variables to change scenarios.

The gameplay of the free-form dive stage is split into four different phases based on the "facilitated workshop framework" offered in Catalano et al. [79], with the phases applying to individual dives, on the micro level, as well as to the entire stay at a given site, on the

macro level. Phases 3 and 4 will not be elaborated on in this thesis, as they stray away too far from the topic of VR Systems and diving simulation. Gameplay beyond phase 2 is however addressed to a certain degree in Guy Kost's thesis [4], which focuses more on the game mechanics in general.

Figure 5.3.: Gameplay flow between the four different phases.

Phase 1: Hub

The hub is the research vessel the player is stationed on. It serves as an interactive main menu and a home base, where the player can plan, research, study, store their gear, and re-familiarise themselves with their dive training. After starting the game, the player avatar is usually spawned inside the hub. To start a dive they have to travel to a new location, if they are not already there, and then start the dive planning. The planning is analogous to real dive planning as taught in the PADI manual, requiring the player to use a simulated dive computer or table to calculate air, decompression stops and more [57]. Should archaeological activities be included in the dive, the player receives a short briefing on the specialised activities the dive entails and is given the option to train in the hub's pool.

In this phase the player should recap their knowledge, training, and information from previous dives, while multimedia content from the briefing is used to gain their interest and excite them for the task ahead [79].

Phase 2: Dive

During the dive phase the player is testing their knowledge and training and applying it to the situation at hand in various individual or collaborative exercises and challenges to

experience and learn in a playful way [78].

Players can either follow a NPC diving buddy or take the lead and have the NPC follow them. While not all dives are of archaeological nature, the most focus is put on those. They often include additional challenges and puzzles based on real underwater archaeological activities, such as photographing, measuring, scanning, collecting, floating, etc. These require players to apply their base virtual diving skills in new and interesting ways while learning about real world UCH preservation and research experientially [79].

Communication during the dive is intentionally limited to non-verbal means to encourage the usage of hand signs [57] and prioritise the active role of the player in the activities instead of having them act as a passive listener [79]. Instead of direct tutorials via popups, or voiceovers (as used in the tutorial stage), hidden tutorials are employed to teach players key elements of design features and gameplay in a way that is believably integrated in the ludonarrative structure of the game. New features that require teaching are first demonstrated in a safe and calm situation combined with an incentive for the player to try it out. Hidden tutorials for very important features are also implemented in a way, that their completion is required for progress and followed by additional or expanded usage of the feature to solidify players familiarity with it [98, 53].

6. Development of the *200Bar* Prototype

To test the validity of certain design choices and as a first step in the execution of the full design into a functional immersive VR diving simulation system, development on a prototype of the previously proposed experience was started. The research and findings showcased throughout this paper were taken into account and the prototype was built according to many best practices to maximise immersion and flow while providing a sufficiently realistic diving experience.

The name, *200Bar*, was chosen as a homage to the initial air pressure in certain DIN diving cylinders. As air is spent during the dive, the full pressure of 200 Bar is only present above the surface, before the dive has started, symbolising the dry nature of our simulator. The specification being part of the German DIN hints at the country of origin.

6.1. Goals and Scope

Early on in the development of the prototype, it was decided that the previously proposed design was not going to be adapted directly, but rather a proof of concept would be build following the same design principles. Building the prototype strictly based on the design could have resulted in too much of the limited time being spent on structural matters, reducing the amount of working content at deadline. Some of the most important features and module functionalities were implemented outside of strict modules to develop a vertical slice of what the full game could be. It was however built in a fashion, that still resembles the modular and variable nature of the design and allows for easy refactoring into the more rigid structure proposed in the design.

The use of prebuilt systems and plugins from outside sources like asset stores and public repositories was seen as a valuable resource. Due to the absence of artists in the development team, assets would have to be either simple block-out prototypes or brought in from outside. In the same spirit, it was deemed as counterproductive to spent valuable development time on systems only tangentially related to the subject of dive simulation, when solutions were already available, allowing the team to focus on the more unique and important systems. Some prebuilt systems might also offer a performance benefit due to their longer development resulting in better optimisations. These assets and systems can either be slowly replaced by original creations over further development or be kept, as middle ware and outside asset use has been a time proven practice in the games industry [99, 100].

6.2. Development Hardware

As VR development is expected to be quite resource intensive, a powerful desktop computer was chosen as the main development platform. The VR HMD used in development is the *Valve Index* in its full *Valve Index VR Kit* configuration, as available on the Steam storefront [84]. It consists of one *Index* HMD, two "*Knuckles*" controllers, and two *Lighthouse 2.0* base stations. The HMD offers a screen resolution of 1440x1600 pixels per eye with a large FOV of 130 degree and a variable screen refresh rate, allowing for 80Hz, 90Hz, 120Hz, and 144Hz. It is tracked in 6DoF using inside-out tracking using the base stations as active markers for effective high precision results [18]. Notably, the headset also offers an innovative off-ear audio solution and an adjustable interpupillary distance slider [84]. Compared to other modern VR HMDs, it offers one of the highest FOVs resulting in a more natural view of the virtual world. The high maximum possible refresh rate of 144Hz is also above the usual 90Hz of competitors, which could help in simulation environments as low refresh rate can lead to a reduced sense of presence and user performance [18].

The "*Knuckles*" controllers are tracked in 6DoF using the same inside-out active marker tracking to calculate their position and orientation in the room, even when not directly visible from the headset. Their most distinct feature however is the strap that allows players to let go of the controller without it falling out of their hands. This can lead to a more natural feel as virtual objects can be picked up using a natural grabbing motion instead of a button. The sensors on the hilt of the controller also allow for individual finger tracking making granular hand gestures possible [18, 84]. Similar to other VR controllers, they offer a two-axis thumbstick on both controllers, two buttons, one analogue trigger, and a small touchpad.

6.3. Software Foundation

The *Unity* game engine was chosen as the development environment for the prototype, fulfilling the role of the core module as laid out in the proposed design. The engine offers support for a large variety of platforms and is known to be very user friendly, in particular for smaller teams with limited team size and strength. VR development is supported out of the box and multiple frameworks can be chosen from, eliminating the need for low-level modification to enable certain features [90]. As our team does not include experienced artists, the native integration of an asset store and import system is an important tool to increase the visual and acoustic fidelity of the virtual environment.

Unity offers one of three different graphics pipelines: *Built-in Render Pipeline*, *Universal Render Pipeline (URP)*, and *High Definition Render Pipeline (HDRP)*. The *Built-in Render Pipeline* was chosen as it has been in development the longest, the majority of assets are made for it, and it reliably supports VR [91].

To increase the variety of compatible HMDs, the *SteamVR* platform was chosen as the

development target. When using the *OpenVR API*, it is possible to target a large variety of VR devices using hardware agnostic interfaces and API calls to access tracking data and device functionality. *Unity* offers support for *OpenVR* and *SteamVR* through an additional plugin, that can be downloaded from the asset store [101, 102].

6.4. Environmental Development

One of the first features addressed in development was the creation of virtual environments, particularly landmasses and bodies of water. While *Unity* provides level building tools, including a terrain editor, it lacks advanced features and is not the easiest to model complex terrain with. For this reason, the *Gaia 2* terrain generator plugin was added to quickly create terrain for development and for its inclusion of various high quality environment art assets. It also offers explicit support for generating simplified terrain fit for use in VR applications [103].

Water and underwater environments make up a majority of the environments encountered in the game, requiring support for performant and realistic looking bodies of water, with great variety in looks and behaviour. After initial experiments with custom shaders failed to produce sufficient results, the *Crest Ocean System* [55] has been elected as the primary water rendering system for the prototype. Its performance centered design is ideal for the use in VR and its in-depth customisation options fit our design principles of variability. Untested in VR applications, the system initially suffered from visual bugs when used in our prototype, but they were fixed over time in cooperation with the *Crest* developers.

Custom Ocean Materials and Wave Spectra were created to fit the locations in the prototype and provide a realistic visual component to the simulation. Both can be adjusted during runtime by changing individual variables or by choosing between presets created during development. To create specialised areas within a bigger body of water, splines can be placed to mark zones, to which different simulation rules apply. This way we created shore waves and calmer or rougher areas in the ocean for a varied and authentic dive experience.

Thanks to the generous contributions of *Unity* asset store developers, we were able to acquire a small collection of realistic underwater flora and fauna assets. These were placed in the underwater environments to enhance the realism and give players a reason to explore.

Two virtual environments were created for the prototype, one as a general test area and development sandbox, titled *Tutorial Cove*, the other as realistic replication of the real world UCH site, *Caesarea Maritima*. Both offer the similar gameplay, but the latter, further detailed in Guy Kost's thesis [4], will likely provide a more authentic experience due to the more carefully crafted environments and use of custom assets.

6.5. Player Controller

The player avatar is the centerpiece of the simulation, allowing players to view and interact with the virtual world through its eyes and body. It is therefore paramount, that any function-

Figure 6.1.: Defining custom shoreline behaviour using splines and shore zones.

Figure 6.2.: Clear blue water preset for use in oceans.

Figure 6.3.: Murky green water preset for possible use in freshwater.

ality, directly relating to the player, works well and without any significant problems. The player controller is the entity that controls the player avatar in most aspects and allows the player to immerse themselves in the virtual world.

As building natural interactive systems in VR requires increased playtesting and development time compared to non-VR systems [56], the *VR Interaction Framework (VRIF)* [104] was chosen as a foundation to build our own systems upon. The *VRIF* provides a number of base features present in various modern VR games and allowed us to focus on the features specific

to dive simulation. This decision was made in response to our observations in other VR diving SGs, where many simple interactions were less than satisfying resulting in an overall drop of immersion and realism.

The Advanced VR Rig added by *VRIF* serves as the basis for our own player controller module, the Advanced Diving Rig, providing hand and head tracking, basic item interaction capabilities, simple ground movement systems, and a small number of helper scripts and objects. With player movement deeply reliant on physics, as can be seen in figure 6.4, the Advanced Diving Rig, initially controlled by *Unity's* default character controller, had to be heavily modified to function on rigid body basis. New colliders were added to support collisions with objects or terrain and the existing smooth locomotion scripts had to be edited to make the physics based locomotion work. To address arising collision problems between the body colliders, hands, and objects, separate layers were created for all and the interactions restricted using the Layer Collision Matrix.

The player controller dynamically switches between locomotion methods based on the circumstances the Advanced Diving Rig is in. When on ground it defaults to either controller based continuous locomotion or controller based instant teleportation, depending on the settings provided by the Player Manager. In water swimming/diving locomotion is activated and once off the ground and sufficiently submerged, ground locomotion is disabled. Buoyancy is applied to the player in two stages, basic buoyancy once the water is entered, and additional BCD buoyancy once the rig is sufficiently submerged (75% by default).

6.5.1. Physics & Buoyancy

The custom physics behaviour created for the player is one of the main features on this prototype and has been a major focus in development. The Advanced Diving Rig can in theory be influenced by the physics engine like any other RigidBody, but the interaction is intentionally limited by allowing only certain interactions to reduce the likelihood of a physics error affecting the player. Early tests using regular imported physics behaviour often produced insufficient or hard to control results, that lead to uncomfortable player movement. It was therefore decided to create custom physics scripts for some of the most important interactions of the player with the world.

There are two central forces that influence the player avatar on a simulated dive, gravity and buoyancy. Gravity is a constant downward force applied to most objects in the *Unity* physics engine by default using the RigidBody component. For the player we wanted full control over physics behaviour and disabled the default gravity to use our own calculation in the Player Buoyancy script. Buoyancy on the other hand is not present in the engine by default and was implemented by us on the basis of real world principles. The big difference between buoyancy and gravity for the player in comparison to other simulated objects in the scene, is that the players physics behaviour is overall dynamic and influenced by many different components, whereas objects use a simplified model, which is elaborated on further below.

Figure 6.4.: Simplified overview of the different subsystems withing the player controller.

As shown in figure 6.5, the rig's buoyancy and gravity are influenced by three main components, the diver itself, the BCD, and the additional essential diving gear (e.g. lead, air cylinder, etc.). Diver and gear are similar in that they have two static variables assigned to them at the beginning of the dive, resulting in static forces that can be calculated once in the beginning and then reused. The BCD is a special case, because its volume can be adjusted during the dive to increase or decrease the buoyant force of the whole rig. Its gravity can not be influenced as the weight remains unchanged during the dive.

Figure 6.5.: The different forces influencing the overall buoyant force applied to the player avatar.

When the dive is started the Player Buoyancy script queries all important variables from the Player Physics Manger, including variables relayed from outside systems (i.e water density), and calculates all static forces once, summing them up into two variables to decrease the necessary operations each time the forces are applied. Additionally a static bcd buoyant force is calculated using the maximum possible inflation of the BCD but not yet added to the other forces, so it can be dynamically modified by the inflation during runtime.

The gravitational force $F_{g_{base}}$ is calculated in the usual way using

$$F_g = m \cdot a = m \cdot g$$

$$F_{g_{base}} = (m_{diver} + m_{bcd} + m_{gear}) \cdot g$$

where m in kg is the mass of a component, a in m/s^2 the acceleration applied to the component, which in this case is the gravitational acceleration g set in the physics settings ($-9.81m/s^2$ by default).

Static buoyancy $F_{b_{static}}$ is calculated with the following formula at startup

$$F_{b_{static}} = (V_{diver} + V_{gear}) \cdot \rho \cdot (-g)$$

where V is the volume in m^3 , ρ the fluid density in kg/m^3 ($1000kg/m^3$ for water), and g in m/s^2 ($-9.81m/s^2$ by default). The dynamic buoyancy of the BCD is calculated by multiplying the maximum possible buoyant force

$$F_{b_{bcdmax}} = (V_{bcdmax}) \cdot \rho \cdot (-g)$$

with the percentage of inflation *inflation* every physics step to calculate an accurate buoyant force at any given time.

Finally, any additional buoyant or gravitational forces added by items the player is currently holding are also added, disabling any force calculations the items would otherwise make to float on their own. The composite buoyant force is multiplied with the percentage of submersion to ensure only parts actually submerged create lifting forces. This results in a final set of 2 dynamic forces, the final buoyant force $F_{b_{final}}$ and the final gravitational force $F_{g_{final}}$, which are updated every physics frame for accurate simulation:

$$F_{b_{final}} = (F_{b_{static}} + (F_{b_{bcdmax}} \cdot inflation\%) + \sum F_{b_{item}}) \cdot submersion\%$$

$$F_{g_{final}} = F_{g_{base}} + \sum F_{g_{item}}$$

6.5.2. Water Movement

In contrast to the proposed design, the swimming and diving locomotion systems have been implemented together in the prototype to allow for faster prototyping and development of the similar systems. The implemented locomotion is closest to the immersive hybrid diving method elaborated in chapter 5, using a mixture of motion based natural swimming and controller based pointing.

Motion based natural swimming tracks the players hands using the handheld controllers and calculates a propulsion vector based on the difference of hand position from one timestep to the next, which can be further amplified using a speed modifier. Players can swim or dive in the game by performing a horizontal breaststroke while standing or sitting in real life, as visualised in figure 6.6.

Initially, we experimented with tracking and converting all significantly large hand movements into locomotion, excluding only a small region in front of the player's body to allow

for the return of hands into the initial breaststroke position without backwards movement. However, this resulted in erratic, unexpected movement that distracted more than it increased realism. The inclusion of hand orientation was also attempted, only applying movement to the player, when the palm of the hand points in the same direction the controller is moving, similar to real swimming where water is scooped with the hands. Again the results were unsatisfactory, and further research into commercial releases using arm movement prompted us to switch to a trigger based approach [52, 51]. Hand movement is only tracked and converted into virtual propulsion when the trigger buttons on both controllers are pressed down. This allows players to precisely control their swimming direction and speed without any unintentional inputs causing confusion or motion sickness.

In addition to the motion tracked approach, it is possible at any time to move the left or right hand to a position in front of the lower chest area to activate the controller based pointing locomotion method. In this mode, the Advanced Diving Rig receives propulsion in the direction the controller is pointing when its trigger is pressed down. The speed can be modified by depressing the trigger further, if an analogue trigger is present (which it is in the *Index "Knuckles"*), or set in a variable in the options.

Both locomotion types work well together and lead to immersive experiences during testing and the reliance of both methods on the trigger could lead to a more clear separation from other inputs, possibly reducing confusion in players.

Finally, players can pick up the LPI from an inventory slot on their virtual waist, to control the amount of air present in the BCD. With LPI in hand the A and B buttons on the top face of the controller can be used to inflate or deflate the BCD volume, which, due to the changes it causes in the buoyancy calculations, causes the player to slowly rise or sink. In our game this is the primary way of controlling the player avatar's depth as breathing and lung volume control are not present. While technically the two previous locomotion types are capable of vertical movement as well, a variable dampening in the up and down direction can be applied to them, in turn encouraging the use of the more realistic BCD locomotion.

6.6. Interactive Objects

To facilitate a more realistic and immersive VR experience, many objects were added throughout the virtual environment, allowing players to interact with more than just their own player avatar. We hope that the presence of these items encourages players to explore on their own with the world, learning about UCH and diving in the process. Interactive objects can be grabbed or moved using the motion tracked controllers, stored in one of the inventory slots at the hips, and do often provide additional gameplay features as shown below.

Figure 6.6.: Conversion of real life breaststrokes to virtual propulsion vectors for immersive swimming and diving.

6.6.1. Object Physics

Many of the interactions between objects, terrain, and players make use of the physics engine to provide realistic and dynamic responses to inputs. *Unity* already offers many of the functionalities needed for basic object physics behavior and *VRIF* helper scripts were employed to build reliable systems for synergy with the player in VR.

For realistic water physics we employ a system adapted from the scripts that govern player physics behaviour and simplified to save computational resources. Objects using this system have variables similar to the VR Diving Rig that change how they behave based on scientific principles. Most notably only these objects communicate with the `Player Physics Manager` to influence the player's buoyancy calculation when held in their inventory.

6.6.2. BCD Low Pressure Inflator

The BCD Low Pressure Inflator (LPI) is perhaps the most important object in the game, and always located in a slot on the player avatar's left shoulder by default. As mentioned previously it allows the precise control of the BCD inflation level using air from the virtual diving cylinder in the process, allowing effective vertical locomotion and trimming in the water. Due to its importance, it can't be removed from the inventory and automatically returns to its slot when dropped.

6.6.3. Submersible Pressure Gauge

The Submersible Pressure Gauge (SPG) is another essential object for any real or simulated dive, and therefore can not be removed from the player's inventory as well. The SPG is connected to the first stage on the air cylinder and indicates the remaining air pressure in the tank on the gauge. During the dive, players have to pay attention to the indicator to not run out of air and plan their ascend in time.

6.6.4. Dive Watch

The dive watch can be found on the avatar's left wrist and does not offer any interactions, displaying important information to the player instead. On its flat surface it shows the depth of the player when underwater, the time passed since the dive was started, and the score acquired up to this point. The first two stats are vital in the execution of a dive and are used to keep track of the remaining air, ascend in time, and include the necessary decompression stops. Should any other variables be important to the player in the future, they might be displayed on the watch too.

6.6.5. Dive Tablet

The diving tablet in our prototype is a multipurpose gameplay tool, implementing an immersive, diegetic UI in the form of a portable tablet PC. It can be used to change certain gameplay settings and is a vital part of the education aspect of the game, by providing

information about discovered archaeological sites, and testing the player's understanding in quizzes.

6.6.6. Slate & Marker

To communicate underwater, divers use hand signs and small whiteboards with waterproof markers, called slates. While there is no multiplayer functionality present in the prototype, the slate was still included to provide realistic note-taking capabilities, as well as a fun toy to play around with. In future updates it could be used for communication with NPCs or other players.

6.6.7. Underwater Camera

Underwater cameras are a great tool for documenting archaeological findings or flora and fauna in the ever changing underwater environments. We originally intended to use an underwater camera as part of the underwater archaeology gameplay, but bugs with the VR rendering and our water system made it too unreliable a feature. However, it is still available for players to experiment with and take screenshots of the experience without breaking immersion.

6.6.8. Collectibles

Collectibles refer to all interactive objects that can be moved or picked up, but do not serve any other purpose. Collectibles hold a variable value that increases a player's score, when placed in a special inventory slot at the left hip of the avatar. This can be used as an incentive for players to explore the virtual underwater world or employed as hint pointing towards a point of interest. Certain collectibles can also decrease the score when picked up or collected, to indicate that certain objects found underwater should be left alone or returned to their origin to preserve the fragile biosphere and invaluable artifacts.

6.7. Gameplay

While much of the prototypes gameplay emerges from the intricate mechanics used to simulate underwater movement and physics as well as the interaction with various objects, specialised gameplay systems and concepts were implemented to increase the players fun and immersion and teach diving and UCH specific knowledge.

After starting the game, the player can choose from two different locations, *Tutorial Cove* and *Caesarea Maritima*. Both offer similar gameplay, but the latter offers a more polished experience and is modelled after a real UCH dive site in Israel. Exposition and a short tutorial are provided via voice over, while the player adjusts to VR and familiarises themselves with the virtual surroundings. Some of the objects mentioned above are obtainable in the immediate vicinity accompanied by text or audio clips that provide context and real information about

Figure 6.7.: Diving equipment with informational tooltips, allowing for closer inspection.

diving, equipment, and UCH (Figure 6.7). Settings can be changed using diegetic UI elements present in the vicinity and one of three play styles can be chosen on the dive tablet that is already present in the inventory. In *Tour* mode the environment can be explored with reduced simulation realism and unlimited air. *Simplified Mode* provides the full simulation experience with all gameplay elements, but simplified air calculations. Selecting *Full Mode* enables the full experience of the game with realistic air consumption, where POIs have to be found, identified, and verified using information about the real *Caesarea Maritima* discovered during the dive. Guy Kost details this gameplay further in his thesis [4].

6.7.1. Points of Interest

Specific areas in the virtual environment are marked as points of interest (POIs) to signify their importance. These spots often include archaeological findings or extraordinary terrain. Most POIs in the prototype are based on real artifacts and include educative content that is sent on the dive tablet. They are also used as puzzle locations for the *Explorer* mode.

6.7.2. Coin & Trash Collection

In both environments, coins and trash can be found and collected to increase the score. Coins in particular are used to lead players to POIs and are modelled after those found in *Caesarea Maritima*. Trash on the other hand can be found on the seabed or floating at the surface and can be picked up to encourage similar behaviour in the real world.

6.8. Challenges & Limitations

VR development can be very challenging and certain aspects of it are a lot more complicated in comparison to normal games. Prototyping and testing in general is a lot more time intensive as the HMD and controllers have to be constantly put on and off. Simple functionalities in VR often require extensive playtesting to feel immersive and require extensive bug fixing, especially when directly related to player interaction. Despite this, we are happy with the prototype's development so far and think it can already provide an immersive gameplay experience and simulate certain aspects of diving authentically.

Many of the modules and functionalities outlined in the proposed design in chapter 5 could not be implemented due to limited time and the small development team. Especially the currently missing support for hardware features like full finger tracking and breathing control could limit the authenticity of the experience. We also think the level of realism in our immersive VR diving simulator could be increased by gaining access to high fidelity assets generated from data and images collected at the real diving location. Chapter 8 outlines some of the possibilities we see for improvements in the prototype and further development of the system.

Figure 6.8.: *Caesarea Maritima* shore with thumbs up.

Figure 6.9.: Possible mode selection using a dive tablet.

Figure 6.10.: Underwater communication using a slate & marker.

Figure 6.11.: Preparing to deflate the BCD at the beginning of a dive.

Figure 6.12.: Diegetic menu to change default variables before a dive.

7. Evaluation

This chapter lays out the design of a theoretical user-study created to evaluate the performance of the prototype in multiple metrics. The study is constructed on the basis of three separate questionnaires, that aim to quantify the individual immersion in the game, the degree of VIMS, the authenticity of the diving experience, and the specific knowledge transfer.

Due to the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, it was not deemed safe to conduct the user-study in person. To ensure a proper evaluation, all participants have to be evaluated in a similar environment, requiring testing in the same location using the same VR hardware setup. Uncertain regulations and fluctuating case numbers made it impossible to host a comprehensive user-study at the time of writing. The methodology developed for the user-study is listed below for a proper study to be conducted at a further time.

Initially, participants are given up to ten minutes to fill out the preliminary section of their questionnaire alone. No questions about the prototype or the virtual experienced are answered yet. Participants are then introduced to the hardware setup of the game and the HMD is adjusted to their preferences. Once in VR the players receive a short briefing of the nature of the experience and the methods of interaction available to them. They are instructed to not ask for help regarding matters of gameplay unless they cannot make progress any other way and are only given the smallest amount of help possible to continue should they ask. The amount of times outside help is required is noted on the questionnaire. Participants are allowed to play the game freely until they choose to stop, their virtual diving cylinder is out of air, or a maximum playtime of 20 minutes is reached. Afterwards they are asked to fill out the postliminary questionnaire.

7.1. Immersive Experience Questionnaire

For our evaluation process we selected The Immersive Experience Questionnaire (IEQ) put forward by Jennett et al. [105] and can be found in addendum A.1. The chosen questionnaire was created as an improvement on a previous version used in two studies. It is partitioned into six categories with four to six questions each: basic attention (four questions), temporal dissociation (six questions), transportation (six questions), challenge (six questions), emotional involvement (five questions) and enjoyment (four questions). After concluding a play session, participants are asked to rate their experience with the game on a scale of 1 to 5. The immersion score is then calculated on a per user basis by taking the sum of the values

assigned to all questions [105].

To validate the questionnaire, a survey was performed with a large sample size of two hundred sixty, made up off 94.3% male and 5.7% female candidates. Participants with recent gaming experience were recruited online and asked to fill out a form consisting of the questionnaire itself and questions on demographic information, either manually entered or selected from a drop-down list of Likert scale [106] options. A factor analysis was performed with the questionnaire determined to be measuring cognitive involvement, emotional involvement (person factors), real world dissociation, challenge, and control (game factors). The overall results were positive [105].

7.2. Virtual Reality Sickness Questionnaire

The Virtual Reality Sickness Questionnaire (VRSQ) we selected for our own evaluation questionnaire is a relatively new design, created for a better evaluation of VIMS specifically in VR applications and can be found in addendum A.2. It was developed by Kim et al. [107] based on the frequently used Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (SSQ) [108]. Sixteen questionnaire items arranged in three categories - nausea, oculomotor, and disorientation - were taken from the SSQ and examined in a case-study. Participants were asked to complete simple control tasks in a VR environment and took the SSQ afterwards. An exploratory factor analysis was performed and duplicate factors, as well as those with factor loadings of less than 0.5, were removed.

The resulting VRSQ consists of nine questions in two components (oculomotor and disorientation) arranged using a Latin-square design and an adjusted computation score for the components and the final result. It shows high correlation to the SSQ in correlation analysis and removes questions unrelated to VR applications, making it more suitable for the evaluation of our prototype [107].

7.3. Diving Experience Questionnaire

To measure the effectiveness of our prototype in authentically simulating the diving experience and its performance as an educational dive training tool, we devised a small set of questions to be added to the overall questionnaire. These questions are split in two sections, one asked before the player experiences the prototype and the other afterwards. Questions can be of three types, a scale from 1 to 5, a binary yes or no question, or an open question, in which participants can note their answers in short texts. The proposed questionnaire can be found in addendum A.3.

7.3.1. Preliminary Questions

The preliminary questions are meant to establish a baseline on the participant, evaluating their previous experience with VR and knowledge of diving. This is important in order to adjust for potential biases caused by extensive previous experience with either, but is also used to weigh postliminary question results, i.e experienced divers could provide further insight in the authenticity of the experience. The questionnaire contains general questions to determine general demographic details, such as age or gender, and binary questions regarding the user's previous experience with the different subjects. Additional space is left after each answer for players to elaborate on their experience if applicable. The results of all preliminary questionnaires would form the body demographic and allows us to determine the weight necessary to compensate for previous experience.

7.3.2. Postliminary Questions

The postliminary questions aim to assess the authenticity of the experience compared to real world diving and tests transfer of specific knowledge. Finally, participants can note individual suggestions on improvements for the game and wishes for new features. The questionnaire will provide a grade of zero to six points of actual knowledge transmission based on the first questions. Each is implemented to test a specific point of knowledge to assess, whether a specific failure in any particular methodology occurred. The following questions will provide a grade generally conveying a participant's feelings about different aspects of the game. The last two questions allow the player to provide input and feedback regarding the game and the user-study. This can prove a valuable source of feedback and inspiration.

7.4. Virtual Questionnaire

With the uncertainty of the COVID-19 pandemic and resulting change of regulations, extensive, properly conducted user-studies might not be possible for a longer time. With the recent rise in consumer adoption of VR HMDs [109], it might be feasible to conduct a virtual user-study with participants using their own headsets. While results could be influenced by non-uniform environments, the questionnaires could be presented in VR, as part of the game itself [110]. A virtual uniform environment could be implemented within the prototype and the questionnaire results uploaded to a remote database.

8. Future Work

In previous chapters we discussed various aspects of dive simulation using VR technology and with the development of the prototype revealed the immense potential for further research in the field. There are multiple opportunities both based on the prototype itself or the proposed design overall, that could be beneficial for the continued sustainable exploitation of UCH and related fields.

The central element of this thesis, the prototype, was developed to implement a first vertical slice of the proposed design and as a testbed for what is possible with modern VR technology. While considerable efforts have already been put into its creation, the prototype is still in an early state and possible future research efforts could be undertaken with its continued development. It is already a highly modular and variable system that can be quickly adapted to fit different scenarios and in turn could be already adjusted for a possible partner for further guided research.

To properly evaluate the design and implementation so far, the proposed user-study should be conducted as soon as possible, so its findings can be used to improve the system early and provide a solid foundation for further versions. Experienced and PADI certified divers could be involved in the user study or included in an additional specialised study to get valuable insight into the level of realism the simulation provides so far and to find possible points of improvements. As the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic might still prohibit extensive in person testing, the proposed ingame virtual questionnaire could still be implemented to get initial data for improvements.

One major point that could be addressed in further development efforts, is the audiovisual fidelity of the experience. The overall quality is already high, as underlying systems are integrated well and work together to form an authentic visual image, but especially individual asset fidelity could still be raised. A cooperation with other researchers, in particular those with access to actual dive sites and data acquisition equipment (both bathymetric scans and photogrammetry) could be used to develop the asset import pipeline proposed in chapter 5 and build an extended repository of realistic models. In return, a version of the prototype would be developed to recreate the environment that was scanned by the cooperation partners, implementing their desired gameplay.

In addition to the authentic visuals, the acoustic experience of the prototype is another area where a collaboration could be beneficial to the continued efforts of the research. Realistic underwater audio samples are generally harder to acquire than other audio clips and require specialised equipment to record. Research presented earlier indicated that acoustic fidelity

has a noticeable impact on immersion and perceived realism and therefore should be one of the next priorities in the development of the prototype.

Lastly, the inclusion of specialised hardware into the design and prototype could be explored for a more immersive and haptic experience. The most promising candidates for this extension are finger tracking as provided by the "*Knuckles*" controllers and breath based buoyancy control using gas flow sensors. Precise tracking of each finger individually would allow users to perform more complex gestures and could be used to include underwater communication on the basis of hand signs in the simulation. Real world divers can modify their body volume by adjusting the depth of their breaths, which causes them to rise or fall in the water. Simulating this technique using additional hardware has been previously linked to higher perceived realism and could facilitate a more effective dive training.

In general we think that there is ample opportunity for future development and research to take place in the field of immersive VR diving simulation SGs. Our prototype and design provide a modular and variable foundation that can be adjusted and expanded to better adapt to specific tasks and on which further work can be conducted. The chapter detailed a small number of possible starting points for us and others to improve on the game itself or implement it in specific use-cases.

9. Conclusion

This thesis aimed to explore the use of modern VR technology and design for the use in SGs to implement a realistic and authentic diving simulation. A comprehensive design for a VR System that can implement such a simulation has been proposed and a prototype was developed to test and validate the design decisions. Throughout the thesis many important findings have been made and could be utilised for the construction of the system.

Initially, we presented our motivations for the thesis and why the topic was chosen to introduce readers to the topic and help them understand the potential outcomes and opportunities stemming from our research. After a brief historical summary of VR technology, an extensive overview of the field was given, explaining the different aspects and advantages of the technology, and definitions for use in the thesis were established. The role and advantage of VR for use in immersive SGs was highlighted and its potential for the use in UCH and dive training.

A number of related works were reviewed to examine the state of the art in the space of VR SGs and dive simulation. Through the study of this previous research we could extract valuable lessons for our own work, helping us with the design and implementation of our own VR system and avoid pitfalls in the progress. This knowledge was promptly applied to the theoretical exploration of the aspects and methods pertaining to the realistic, interactive simulation of a dive. The different sensory stimuli of the activity were brought up and possible technological, as well as design, solutions for their authentic translation into VR was discussed. Based on the results of this consideration, an extensive design for a modular and extensible VR diving simulation system was proposed, detailing both the hardware and software structures along with the underlying principles and philosophies. In cooperation with Guys Kost one possible experience for the system was envisioned aided by his findings in his own thesis. A prototype VR SG based on the previously proposed gameplay and design were then developed in partnership, with components pertaining specifically to dive simulation and VR elaborated here. Finally a user-study was planned for further evaluation of the prototype and the future possibilities resulting from the thesis were explored.

We found that Virtual Reality is likely a suitable technology for the realistic simulation of diving in the context of a Serious Game, in particular when an immersive and realistic virtual environment is used in conjunction with authentic, engaging gameplay. Our prototype provides an early look at the possibilities of such a simulator and could be used to facilitate immersive entertainment or accessible dive training in the future. We intend to further evaluate the performance of the system with the proposed user-study and plan to continue development and research of the prototype in subsequent works.

A. General Addenda

A.1. Immersive Experience Questionnaire (IEQ)

The first of three questionnaires presented to players after their play session is over. Adapted from Jennet et al. [105].

Your experience of the game

Please answer the following questions by circling the relevant number. In particular, remember that these questions are asking you about how you felt at the end of the game.

- To what extent did the game hold your attention?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || A lot

- To what extent did you feel you were focused on the game?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || A lot

- How much effort did you put into playing the game?

Very little || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || A lot

- Did you feel that you were trying your best?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very much so

- To what extent did you lose track of time?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || A lot

- To what extent did you feel consciously aware of being in the real world whilst playing?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very much so

A. General Addenda

- To what extent did you forget about your everyday concerns?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || A lot

- To what extent were you aware of yourself in your surroundings?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very aware

- To what extent did you notice events taking place around you?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || A lot

- Did you feel the urge at any point to stop playing and see what was happening around you?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very much so

- To what extent did you feel that you were interacting with the game environment?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very much so

- To what extent did you feel as though you were separated from your real-world environment?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very much so

- To what extent did you feel that the game was something you were experiencing, rather than something you were just doing?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very much so

- To what extent was your sense of being in the game environment stronger than your sense of being in the real world?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very much so

A. General Addenda

- At any point did you find yourself become so involved that you were unaware you were even using controls?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very much so

- To what extent did you feel as though you were moving through the game according to your own will?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very much so

- To what extent did you find the game challenging?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very difficult

- Were there any times during the game in which you just wanted to give up?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || A lot

- To what extent did you feel motivated while playing?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || A lot

- To what extent did you find the game easy?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very much so

- To what extent did you feel like you were making progress towards the end of the game?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || A lot

- How well do you think you performed in the game?

Very poor || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very well

- To what extent did you feel emotionally attached to the game?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very much so

A. General Addenda

- To what extent were you interested in seeing how the game's events would progress?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || A lot

- How much did you want to "win" the game?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very much so

- Were you in suspense about whether or not you would win or lose the game?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very much so

- At any point did you find yourself become so involved that you wanted to speak to the game directly?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very much so

- To what extent did you enjoy the graphics and the imagery?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || A lot

- How much would you say you enjoyed playing the game?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || A lot

- When interrupted, were you disappointed that the game was over?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very much so

- Would you like to play the game again?

Definitely not || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Definitely yes

A.2. Virtual Reality Sickness Questionnaire (VRSQ)

The first of three questionnaires presented to players after their play session is over. Adapted from Kim et al. [107].

Negative experience with the game

Please rate the severeness of any symptom you might have experienced during the gameplay by circling the appropriate number below.

- General discomfort

Not at all || 0 | 1 | 2 | 3 || Very much

- Fatigue

Not at all || 0 | 1 | 2 | 3 || Very much

- Eyestrain

Not at all || 0 | 1 | 2 | 3 || Very much

- Difficulty focusing

Not at all || 0 | 1 | 2 | 3 || Very much

- Headache

Not at all || 0 | 1 | 2 | 3 || Very much

- Fullness of head

Not at all || 0 | 1 | 2 | 3 || Very much

- Blurred vision

Not at all || 0 | 1 | 2 | 3 || Very much

A. General Addenda

- Dizzy (eyes closed)

Not at all || 0 | 1 | 2 | 3 || Very much

- Vertigo

Not at all || 0 | 1 | 2 | 3 || Very much

A.3. Diving Experience Questionnaire

A.3.1. Preliminary Questionnaire

This questionnaire will precede the play session and is intended to determine demographic details and previous experience.

Personal details and previous experiences

Please answer the following questions by circling the relevant answer or writing in the designated blank areas.

- Age: _____
- Gender: _____ (please leave blank if you would rather not say)
- Do you have previous experience with real world diving?

YES | NO

- If yes, please describe shortly:

A. General Addenda

- Have you previously played any videogame that involved diving?

YES | NO

- If yes, please describe shortly:

- Do you have previous experience with Virtual Reality?

YES | NO

- If yes please describe shortly:

A.3.2. Postliminary Questionnaire

This questionnaire will be presented to players after they finish their play session and is intended to test the quality of knowledge transmission in the game.

What you learned in the game

Please answer the following questions by circling the relevant answer or number, or by writing in the designated blank areas. In particular, remember that these questions are asking you about what you learned while playing the game and how you felt about the learning experience.

- Which device is used to adjust buoyancy during a dive?

- What is the depth at which the ruins of the jetty lie?

- Does depth influence the air consumption rate?

YES | NO

- What are two pieces of equipment included in the scuba kit?

1. -----

2. -----

- Is it correct that surfacing without a safety stop poses no risk to the diver?

YES | NO

- Would you say that it is possible to train diving in a VR game?

Strongly disagree || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Strongly agree

A. General Addenda

- Do you think the game was a realistic portrayal of diving?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very much

- Did you feel like you learned useful information in the game?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very much

- Did you enjoy the learning experience in the game?

Boring || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Enjoyable

- Was the information presented in an interesting manner?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very interesting

- Would you consider games such as this one as a useful tool to deliver information?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very much

- Would you be interested in learning more about diving after playing the game?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very much

- Did you think the way the game presented the information was believable?

Not at all || 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 || Very much

- Do you have any suggestions or wishes for the game?

A. General Addenda

- Do you have any additional feedback?

A.4. Asset Credits

This addendum provides credits to all external assets used in the demo that require it. All items have been lightly modified to work in the *Unity* engine.

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Glossary

Augmented Reality A technological variant of VR in which additional computer-generated information is layered on top of the real-world view of the user. 5, 81

Buoyancy Control Device A multi component device in the shape of a vest used by divers to control their buoyancy and attach additional gear to. 22, 36, 81

Cave Automatic Virtual Environment Cave Automatic Virtual Environment or CAVEs are large partially open boxes that can display images on some sides to create an immersive virtual environment. 6, 7, 29, 81

Degrees of Freedom Describes how many axis of location or rotation are available for movement or tracking. 18, 81

Deutsche Industrie Norm A German industrial standard used in the entire world. 81

Field of View The degree to which an environment is observable by a human or camera. 1, 28, 81

Inverse Kinematics Mathematical procedure of calculating joint positions based on constraints in a kinematic chain. Used in game development for more accurate animations. Inverse Kinematic solvers are programs computing these positions. 23, 81

Low Pressure Inflator Mechanism used to inflate or deflate the air bladders in the BCD. 38, 54, 81

Mixed Reality A technological variant of VR in which 3D computer-generated objects or imagery and real-world 3D environment are mixed. 5, 81

Professional Association of Diving Instructors An organisation that offers licensed membership to recreational divers, as well as organizes diver training on various levels of specialty and difficulty. 2, 81

Serious Game A game with a primary focus beyond entertainment. 9, 81

Underwater Cultural Heritage A collection of all physical evidence and markers of human culture's existence that can be found underwater. This includes any artificial or man-made artefacts as well as flora, fauna, topology and any other natural element found underwater. 2, 81

Virtual Reality A simulated experience that is used primarily for purposes of entertainment and education. Typically involves a computer-generated 3D environment viewed via a HMD. iv, 1, 5, 6, 81

Visually Induced Motion Sickness Condition that can arise when the movement observed by the eyes does not match the movement reported by other senses. 13, 21, 81

Acronyms

3D Three Dimensional. 1, 3, 11, 12, 14, 15, 17, 79, 80

AR Augmented Reality. 5

BCD Buoyancy Control Device. 22, 36–38, 48, 50–52, 54, 59, 78

CAVE Cave Automatic Virtual Environment. 6, 7, 29–31

DIN Deutsche Industrie Norm. 44

DoF Degrees of Freedom. 18, 30, 45

FOV Field of View. 1, 12, 23, 24, 28, 29, 36, 45

HMD Head-Mounted Display. 2–4, 6, 7, 12, 13, 15–18, 24, 29–34, 45, 57, 60, 62, 80

IK Inverse Kinematics. 23, 38

LPI Low Pressure Inflator. 38, 52, 54

MR Mixed Reality. 5

NPC Non-player character. 41, 43, 55

PADI Professional Association of Diving Instructors. 2, 20, 40–42, 63

PC Personal Computer. 9, 28, 54

POI Point of Interest. 16, 56

SG Serious Game. 2, 4, 5, 9–12, 17, 18, 25, 48, 64, 65

UCH Underwater Cultural Heritage. 2, 4, 10–12, 39–41, 43, 46, 52, 55, 56, 63, 65

UI User Interface. 39, 54

VIMS Visually Induced Motion Sickness. 13, 21, 34, 35, 60, 61

VR Virtual Reality. iii, iv, 1–14, 16–30, 32–36, 40–42, 44–48, 52, 54, 55, 57, 60–65, 79

Bibliography

- [1] Alta Reality. *A Township Tale*. 2017. URL: <https://townshiptale.com/> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [2] D. A. Bowman and R. P. McMahan. 'Virtual Reality: How Much Immersion Is Enough?' In: *Computer* 40.7 (2007), pp. 36–43. ISSN: 0018-9162. DOI: 10.1109/MC.2007.257.
- [3] Katharina Jochum. "2021 wird das Jahr der Virtual Reality". 2020. URL: <https://www.immersivelearning.news/2020/10/29/2021-wird-das-jahr-der-virtual-reality/> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [4] Guy Kost. 'Examination of the role of Game Mechanics in Serious Games via analysis of an underwater archaeology simulation VR serious game'. Bachelor Thesis. Technical University Munich, 2021.
- [5] A. Artaud. *The theater and its double*. New York: Grove Weidenfeld, 1958. ISBN: 0802150306.
- [6] Naval Air Station Fort Lauderdale Museum. *The Link Trainer Flight Simulator*. 2010. URL: <https://www.nasflmuseum.com/link-trainer.html> (visited on 11/11/2021).
- [7] Stanley G Weinbaum. *Pygmalion's Spectacles*. 1935. ISBN: 978-1169173781.
- [8] P. Nicholls. *The science fiction encyclopedia*. 1st ed. Garden City N.Y.: Doubleday, 1979. ISBN: 0385130007.
- [9] J. Turi. *The sights and scents of the Sensorama Simulator*. 2014. URL: <https://www.engadget.com/2014-02-16-morton-heiligs-sensorama-simulator.html> (visited on 11/11/2021).
- [10] M. L. Heilig. 'EL Cine del Futuro: The Cinema of the Future'. In: *Presence: Teleoperators and Virtual Environments* 1.3 (1992), pp. 279–294. ISSN: 1054-7460. DOI: 10.1162/pres.1992.1.3.279.
- [11] Holly Brockwell. *Forgotten genius: the man who made a working VR machine in 1957*. 2016. URL: <https://www.techradar.com/news/wearables/forgotten-genius-the-man-who-made-a-working-vr-machine-in-1957-1318253/2> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [12] Paul Sorene. *Jaron Lanier's EyePhone: Head And Glove Virtual Reality In The 1980s*. 2014. URL: <https://flashbak.com/jaron-laniers-eyephone-head-and-glove-virtual-reality-in-the-1980s-26180/> (visited on 11/11/2021).
- [13] Lois Rosson. *The Virtual Interface Environment Workstation (VIEW)*. 2014. URL: https://www.nasa.gov/ames/spinoff/new_continent_of_ideas/ (visited on 11/11/2021).
- [14] Nostalgia Nerd. *The Story of Virtuality*. 2019. URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_X_E_Kg9roE (visited on 11/11/2021).

- [15] William Seibert. *Virtual Reality Then: A Look Back at the Nintendo Virtual Boy*. 2017. URL: <https://www.techspot.com/article/1085-nintendo-virtual-boy/> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [16] Matthew Schnipper. *The Rise and Fall and Rise of Virtual Reality*. 2014. URL: <https://www.theverge.com/a/virtual-reality> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [17] Paul James. *30 Minutes Inside Valve's Prototype Virtual Reality Headset: Owlchemy Labs Share Their Steam Dev Days Experience*. 2014. URL: <https://www.roadtovr.com/hands-valves-virtual-reality-hmd-owlchemy-labs-share-steam-dev-days-experiences/> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [18] V. Angelov, E. Petkov, G. Shipkovenski and T. Kalushkov. 'Modern Virtual Reality Headsets'. In: *2020 International Congress on Human-Computer Interaction, Optimization and Robotic Applications (HORA)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 1–5. ISBN: 978-1-7281-9352-6. DOI: 10.1109/HORA49412.2020.9152604.
- [19] Online Etymology Dictionary. *Definition of virtual*. 2021. URL: <https://www.etymonline.com/search?q=virtual> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [20] Online Etymology Dictionary. *Definition of reality*. 2021. URL: <https://www.etymonline.com/search?q=reality> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [21] Merriam-Webster. *Definition of virtual reality*. 2021. URL: <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/virtual%20reality> (visited on 10/11/2021).
- [22] P. Milgram and F. Kishino. 'A Taxonomy of Mixed Reality Visual Displays'. In: *IEICE Trans. Information Systems* vol. E77-D, no. 12 (1994), pp. 1321–1329.
- [23] M. Carrozzino and M. Bergamasco. 'Beyond virtual museums: Experiencing immersive virtual reality in real museums'. In: *Journal of Cultural Heritage* 11.4 (2010), pp. 452–458. ISSN: 12962074. DOI: 10.1016/j.culher.2010.04.001.
- [24] C. Cruz-Neira, D. J. Sandin, T. A. DeFanti, R. V. Kenyon and J. C. Hart. 'The CAVE: audio visual experience automatic virtual environment'. In: *Communications of the ACM* 35.6 (1992), pp. 64–72. ISSN: 0001-0782. DOI: 10.1145/129888.129892.
- [25] D. R. Mestre. 'CAVE versus Head-Mounted Displays: Ongoing thoughts'. In: *Electronic Imaging* 2017.3 (2017), pp. 31–35. ISSN: 2470-1173. DOI: 10.2352/ISSN.2470-1173.2017.3.ERVR-094.
- [26] J. Mütterlein. 'The Three Pillars of Virtual Reality? Investigating the Roles of Immersion, Presence, and Interactivity'. In: *Proceedings of the 51st Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*. Ed. by T. Bui. Proceedings of the Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences. Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences, 2018. DOI: 10.24251/HICSS.2018.174.
- [27] J. Nakamura and M. Csikszentmihalyi. 'Flow Theory and Research'. In: *Oxford handbook of positive psychology*. Ed. by C. R. Snyder and S. J. Lopez. Oxford library of psychology. New York: Oxford University Press, 2009, pp. 194–206. ISBN: 9780195187243. DOI: 10.1093/oxfordhb/9780195187243.013.0018.

- [28] J. J. Cummings and J. N. Bailenson. 'How Immersive Is Enough? A Meta-Analysis of the Effect of Immersive Technology on User Presence'. In: *Media Psychology* 19.2 (2016), pp. 272–309. ISSN: 1521-3269. DOI: 10.1080/15213269.2015.1015740.
- [29] R. P. McMahan, D. A. Bowman, D. J. Zielinski and R. B. Brady. 'Evaluating display fidelity and interaction fidelity in a virtual reality game'. In: *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* 18.4 (2012), pp. 626–633. ISSN: 1077-2626. DOI: 10.1109/TVCG.2012.43.
- [30] S. Hudson, S. Matson-Barkat, N. Pallamin and G. Jegou. 'With or without you? Interaction and immersion in a virtual reality experience'. In: *Journal of Business Research* 100 (2019), pp. 459–468. ISSN: 01482963. DOI: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2018.10.062.
- [31] B. Laha, K. Sensharma, J. D. Schiffbauer and D. A. Bowman. 'Effects of immersion on visual analysis of volume data'. In: *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* 18.4 (2012), pp. 597–606. ISSN: 1077-2626. DOI: 10.1109/TVCG.2012.42.
- [32] D. Weibel and B. Wissmath. 'Immersion in Computer Games: The Role of Spatial Presence and Flow'. In: *International Journal of Computer Games Technology* 2011 (2011), pp. 1–14. ISSN: 1687-7047. DOI: 10.1155/2011/282345.
- [33] L. Zhang, D. A. Bowman and C. N. Jones. 'Exploring Effects of Interactivity on Learning with Interactive Storytelling in Immersive Virtual Reality'. In: *2019 11th International Conference on Virtual Worlds and Games for Serious Applications (VS-Games)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 1–8. ISBN: 978-1-7281-4540-2. DOI: 10.1109/VS-Games.2019.8864531.
- [34] M. W. Martin and Y. Shen. 'Defining and Leveraging Game Qualities for Serious Games'. In: *Selected Papers and Presentations Presented at MODSIM World 2010 Conference Expo*. 2011. URL: <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/citations/20110012076>.
- [35] D. Checa and A. Bustillo. 'A review of immersive virtual reality serious games to enhance learning and training'. In: *Multimedia Tools and Applications* 79.9-10 (2020), pp. 5501–5527. ISSN: 1380-7501. DOI: 10.1007/s11042-019-08348-9.
- [36] K. Ahir, K. Govani, R. Gajera and M. Shah. 'Application on Virtual Reality for Enhanced Education Learning, Military Training and Sports'. In: *Augmented Human Research* 5.1 (2020). ISSN: 2365-4317. DOI: 10.1007/s41133-019-0025-2.
- [37] E. Aksoy. 'Comparing the Effects on Learning Outcomes of Tablet-Based and Virtual Reality-Based Serious Gaming Modules for Basic Life Support Training: Randomized Trial'. In: *JMIR serious games* 7.2 (2019), e13442. ISSN: 2291-9279. DOI: 10.2196/13442.
- [38] Y. Shu, Y.-Z. Huang, S.-H. Chang and M.-Y. Chen. 'Do virtual reality head-mounted displays make a difference? A comparison of presence and self-efficacy between head-mounted displays and desktop computer-facilitated virtual environments'. In: *Virtual Reality* 23.4 (2019), pp. 437–446. ISSN: 1359-4338. DOI: 10.1007/s10055-018-0376-x.

- [39] O. S. Itani and L. D. Hollebeek. 'Light at the end of the tunnel: Visitors' virtual reality (versus in-person) attraction site tour-related behavioral intentions during and post-COVID-19'. In: *Tourism Management* 84 (2021), p. 104290. ISSN: 02615177. DOI: 10.1016/j.tourman.2021.104290.
- [40] AtlasV. *The Dawn of Art*. 2020. URL: <https://atlasv.io/projects/dawn-of-art/> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [41] R. P. de Lope and N. Medina-Medina. 'A Comprehensive Taxonomy for Serious Games'. In: *Journal of Educational Computing Research* 55.5 (2017), pp. 629–672. ISSN: 0735-6331. DOI: 10.1177/0735633116681301.
- [42] Ballast Technologies. *DIVR*. 2021. URL: <https://www.ballastvr.com/divr> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [43] Ballast Technologies. *VRSlide*. 2021. URL: <https://www.ballastvr.com/vrslide> (visited on 13/11/2021).
- [44] G. Fauville, A. C. M. Queiroz, E. S. Woolsey, J. W. Kelly and J. N. Bailenson. 'The effect of water immersion on vection in virtual reality'. In: *Scientific Reports* 11.1 (2021), p. 1022. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-020-80100-y.
- [45] VISAS Project. *VISAS Project Website*. 2018. URL: <http://www.visas-project.eu/en/> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [46] F. Bruno, A. Lagudi, L. Barbieri, M. Muzzupappa, G. Ritacco, A. Cozza, M. Cozza, R. Peluso, M. Lupia and G. Cario. 'Virtual and Augmented Reality Tools to Improve the Exploitation of Underwater Archaeological Sites by Diver and Non-diver Tourists'. In: *Digital Heritage. Progress in Cultural Heritage: Documentation, Preservation, and Protection*. Ed. by M. Ioannides, E. Fink, A. Moropoulou, M. Hagedorn-Saupe, A. Fresa, G. Liestøl, V. Rajcic and P. Grussenmeyer. Vol. 10058. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2016, pp. 269–280. ISBN: 978-3-319-48495-2. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-48496-9_22.
- [47] F. Bruno, A. Lagudi, L. Barbieri, M. Muzzupappa, M. Mangeruga, F. Pupo, M. Cozza, A. Cozza, G. Ritacco, R. Peluso and S. Tusa. 'Virtual Diving in the Underwater Archaeological Site of Cala Minnola'. In: *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences XLII-2/W3* (2017), pp. 121–126. DOI: 10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-2-W3-121-2017.
- [48] F. Bruno, L. Barbieri, A. Lagudi, M. Cozza, A. Cozza, R. Peluso and M. Muzzupappa. 'Virtual dives into the underwater archaeological treasures of South Italy'. In: *Virtual Reality* 22.2 (2018), pp. 91–102. ISSN: 1359-4338. DOI: 10.1007/s10055-017-0318-z.
- [49] VISAS Project. *VISAS Project Services Website*. 2018. URL: <http://www.visas-project.eu/en/services-en.html> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [50] J. L. Soler-Domínguez, C. de Juan, M. Contero and M. Alcañiz. 'I walk, therefore I am: a multidimensional study on the influence of the locomotion method upon presence in virtual reality'. In: *Journal of Computational Design and Engineering* 7.5 (2020), pp. 577–590. DOI: 10.1093/jcde/qwaa040.

- [51] Archiact. *Freediver: Triton Down*. 2019. URL: https://store.steampowered.com/app/995230/FREEDIVER_Triton_Down/ (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [52] Respawn Entertainment. *Medal of Honor™: Above and Beyond*. 2020. URL: <https://www.ea.com/games/medal-of-honor/medal-of-honor-above-and-beyond> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [53] Valve Software. *Half-Life: Alyx Developer Commentary*. 2020. URL: https://store.steampowered.com/app/546560/HalfLife_Alyx/ (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [54] E. D. Ragan, D. A. Bowman, R. Kopper, C. Stinson, S. Scerbo and R. P. McMahan. 'Effects of Field of View and Visual Complexity on Virtual Reality Training Effectiveness for a Visual Scanning Task'. In: *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* 21.7 (2015), pp. 794–807. ISSN: 1077-2626. DOI: 10.1109/TVCG.2015.2403312.
- [55] Wave Harmonic. *Crest Ocean System*. 2017. URL: <https://github.com/wave-harmonic/crest> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [56] Kerry Davis. *VR Development*. 2019. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=80WjxGL8PDM> (visited on 04/11/2021).
- [57] PADI. *Open water diver manual*. PADI, 2015. ISBN: 978-1-878663-16-0.
- [58] C. Boletsis and J. E. Cedergren. 'VR Locomotion in the New Era of Virtual Reality: An Empirical Comparison of Prevalent Techniques'. In: *Advances in Human-Computer Interaction 2019* (2019), pp. 1–15. ISSN: 1687-5893. DOI: 10.1155/2019/7420781.
- [59] Teresa Carey. *The surprising cure to cybersickness – using vr underwater*. 2021. URL: <https://www.freethink.com/health/cybersickness-cure> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [60] D. Jain, M. Sra, J. Guo, R. Marques, R. Wu, J. Chiu and C. Schmandt. 'Immersive Scuba Diving Simulator Using Virtual Reality'. In: *Proceedings of the 29th Annual Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology*. New York, NY, USA: ACM, 2016. DOI: 10.1145/2984511.2984519.
- [61] Merriam-Webster. *Definition of haptics*. 2021. URL: <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/haptics> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [62] J. Kreimeier, S. Hammer, D. Friedmann, P. Karg, C. Bühner, L. Bankel and T. Götzelmann. 'Evaluation of different types of haptic feedback influencing the task-based presence and performance in virtual reality'. In: *Proceedings of the 12th ACM International Conference on Pervasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments*. Ed. by F. Makedon. New York, NY, USA: ACM, 2019, pp. 289–298. ISBN: 9781450362320. DOI: 10.1145/3316782.3321536.
- [63] R. L. Peiris, L. Chan and K. Minamizawa. 'LiquidReality: Wetness Sensations on the Face for Virtual Reality'. In: Springer, Cham, 2018, pp. 366–378. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-93399-3_32. URL: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-93399-3_32.

- [64] J. Gugenheimer, D. Wolf, E. R. Eiriksson, P. Maes and E. Rukzio. 'GyroVR'. In: *Proceedings of the 29th Annual Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology*. Ed. by J. Rekimoto, T. Igarashi, J. O. Wobbrock and D. Avrahami. New York, NY, USA: ACM, 2016, pp. 227–232. ISBN: 9781450341899. DOI: 10.1145/2984511.2984535.
- [65] Manus VR. *Manus VR Website*. 2021. URL: <https://www.manus-vr.com/haptic-gloves> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [66] HaptX. *HaptX Website*. 2021. URL: <https://haptx.com/> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [67] Merriam-Webster. *Definition of kinesthesia*. 2021. URL: <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/kinesthesia> (visited on 10/11/2021).
- [68] Valve Software. *Half-Life: Alyx - Locomotion Deep Dive*. 2020. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TX58AbJq-xo> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [69] B. Caola, M. Montalti, A. Zanini, A. Leadbetter and M. Martini. 'The Bodily Illusion in Adverse Conditions: Virtual Arm Ownership During Visuomotor Mismatch'. In: *Perception* 47.5 (2018), p. 301006618758211. ISSN: 0301-0066. DOI: 10.1177/0301006618758211.
- [70] M. Parger, J. H. Mueller, D. Schmalstieg and M. Steinberger. 'Human upper-body inverse kinematics for increased embodiment in consumer-grade virtual reality'. In: *Proceedings of the 24th ACM Symposium on Virtual Reality Software and Technology*. Ed. by S. N. Spencer, S. Morishima, Y. Itoh, T. Shiratori, Y. Yue and R. Lindeman. New York, NY, USA: ACM, 2018, pp. 1–10. ISBN: 9781450360869. DOI: 10.1145/3281505.3281529.
- [71] M. Lindquist, B. Maxim, J. Proctor and F. Dolins. 'The effect of audio fidelity and virtual reality on the perception of virtual greenspace'. In: *Landscape and Urban Planning* 202 (2020), p. 103884. ISSN: 01692046. DOI: 10.1016/j.landurbplan.2020.103884.
- [72] Dartmouth Undergraduate Journal of Science. *The Underwater Propagation of Sound and its Applications*. 2012. URL: <https://sites.dartmouth.edu/dujs/2012/03/11/the-underwater-propagation-of-sound-and-its-applications/> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [73] R. Ding and S. Liu. 'Underwater sound propagation for virtual environments'. In: *The Visual Computer* 37.9-11 (2021), pp. 2797–2807. ISSN: 0178-2789. DOI: 10.1007/s00371-021-02175-6.
- [74] Valve Software. *Half-Life: Alyx*. 2020. URL: https://store.steampowered.com/app/546560/HalfLife_Alyx/ (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [75] J. Clark, A. Fletcher, T. Fritz and J. Schreiber. 'Modular educational game system: A customizable framework for learning'. In: *2011 16th International Conference on Computer Games (CGAMES)*. IEEE, 2011, pp. 248–253. ISBN: 978-1-4577-1451-1. DOI: 10.1109/CGAMES.2011.6000347.
- [76] D. L. Parnas, P. C. Clements and D. M. Weiss. 'The Modular Structure of Complex Systems'. In: *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering* SE-11.3 (1985), pp. 259–266. ISSN: 0098-5589. DOI: 10.1109/TSE.1985.232209.

- [77] Facebook Technologies. *Oculus Developer Resources*. 2021. URL: <https://developer.oculus.com/resources/> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [78] P. Lamer, S. Arnab, I. Dunwell, C. Stewart, S. Clarke and P. Petridis. 'Essential features of serious games design in higher education: Linking learning attributes to game mechanics'. In: *British Journal of Educational Technology* 48.4 (2017), pp. 972–994. ISSN: 00071013. DOI: 10.1111/bjet.12467.
- [79] C. E. Catalano, A. M. Luccini and M. Mortara. 'Guidelines for an effective design of serious games'. In: *International Journal of Serious Games* 1.1 (2014). DOI: 10.17083/ijsg.v1i1.8.
- [80] Valve Software. *Steam Hardware Survey*. 2021. URL: <https://store.steampowered.com/hwsurvey> (visited on 13/11/2021).
- [81] Facebook Technologies. *Oculus Website*. 2021. URL: <https://www.oculus.com/> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [82] P. Havig, J. McIntire and E. Geiselman. 'Virtual reality in a cave: limitations and the need for HMDs?' In: *Head- and Helmet-Mounted Displays XVI: Design and Applications*. Ed. by P. L. Marasco and P. R. Havig. SPIE Proceedings. SPIE, 2011, p. 804107. DOI: 10.1117/12.883855.
- [83] M. Cordeil, T. Dwyer, K. Klein, B. Laha, K. Marriott and B. H. Thomas. 'Immersive Collaborative Analysis of Network Connectivity: CAVE-style or Head-Mounted Display?' In: *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* 23.1 (2017), pp. 441–450. ISSN: 1077-2626. DOI: 10.1109/TVCG.2016.2599107.
- [84] Valve Software. *Valve Index Website*. 2021. URL: <https://www.valvesoftware.com/en/index/> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [85] Ultraleap. *Leap Motion Controller Website*. 2021. URL: <https://www.ultraleap.com/product/leap-motion-controller/> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [86] RootMotion. *Final IK*. 2014. URL: <https://assetstore.unity.com/packages/tools/animation/final-ik-14290> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [87] J.-m. Cho, Y.-d. Kim, S. H. Jung, H. Shin and T. Kim. '78-4: Screen Door Effect Mitigation and Its Quantitative Evaluation in VR Display'. In: *SID Symposium Digest of Technical Papers* 48.1 (2017), pp. 1154–1156. ISSN: 0097966X. DOI: 10.1002/sdtp.11847.
- [88] Kiwi Design. *Kiwi Design Website*. 2021. URL: <https://www.kiwidesign.shop/> (visited on 13/11/2021).
- [89] Epic Games. *Unreal Engine*. 2021. URL: <https://www.unrealengine.com/en-US/> (visited on 13/11/2021).
- [90] Unity Technologies. *Unity Engine*. 2021. URL: <https://unity.com/> (visited on 13/11/2021).
- [91] Unity Technologies. *Unity Manual: Render Pipelines Introduction*. 2021. URL: <https://docs.unity3d.com/Manual/render-pipelines-overview.html> (visited on 12/11/2021).

- [92] Unity Technologies. *Editor XR*. 2021. URL: <https://unity.com/editorxr> (visited on 13/11/2021).
- [93] L. J. Hettinger and G. E. Riccio. 'Visually Induced Motion Sickness in Virtual Environments'. In: *Presence: Teleoperators and Virtual Environments* 1.3 (1992), pp. 306–310. ISSN: 1054-7460. DOI: 10.1162/pres.1992.1.3.306.
- [94] C. Boletsis. 'The New Era of Virtual Reality Locomotion: A Systematic Literature Review of Techniques and a Proposed Typology'. In: *Multimodal Technologies and Interaction* 1.4 (2017), p. 24. DOI: 10.3390/mti1040024.
- [95] M. P. Jacob Habgood, D. Moore, D. Wilson and S. Alapont. 'Rapid, Continuous Movement Between Nodes as an Accessible Virtual Reality Locomotion Technique'. In: *2018 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces (VR)*. IEEE, 2018, pp. 371–378. ISBN: 978-1-5386-3365-6. DOI: 10.1109/VR.2018.8446130.
- [96] E. Prado, M. Gómez-Ballesteros, A. Cobo, F. Sánchez, A. Rodríguez-Basalo, B. Arrese and L. Rodríguez-Cobo. '3d modeling of Rio Miera wreck ship merging optical and multibeam high resolution points cloud'. In: *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences XLII-2/W10* (2019), pp. 159–165. DOI: 10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-2-W10-159-2019.
- [97] PADI. *PADI Course Catalog*. 2021. URL: <https://www.padi.com/courses> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [98] Game Maker's Toolkit. *Half-Life 2's Invisible Tutorial*. 2015. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MMggqenxuZc> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [99] GamesIndustry International. *Money Games: The Middleware Opportunity*. 2011. URL: <https://www.gamesindustry.biz/articles/2011-04-14-money-games-the-middleware-opportunity-article> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [100] Kid Leaves Stoop. *The most overused game graphic you never noticed | Texture Archaeology*. 2021. URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bsCN0Yx2Vbs> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [101] Valve Software. *OpenVR API Documentation*. 2020. URL: <https://github.com/ValveSoftware/openvr/wiki/API-Documentation> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [102] Valve Software. *Steam VR Website*. 2021. URL: <https://www.steamvr.com/> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [103] Procedural Worlds. *Gaia 2 - Terrain & Scene Generator*. 2015. URL: <https://assetstore.unity.com/packages/tools/terrain/gaia-2-terrain-scene-generator-42618> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [104] Bearded Ninja Games. *VR Interaction Framework*. 2020. URL: <https://assetstore.unity.com/packages/templates/systems/vr-interaction-framework-161066> (visited on 12/11/2021).

- [105] C. Jennett, A. L. Cox, P. Cairns, S. Dhoparee, A. Epps, T. Tijs and A. Walton. 'Measuring and defining the experience of immersion in games'. In: *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies* 66.9 (2008), pp. 641–661. ISSN: 10715819. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijhcs.2008.04.004.
- [106] A. Joshi, S. Kale, S. Chandel and D. Pal. 'Likert Scale: Explored and Explained'. In: *British Journal of Applied Science & Technology* 7.4 (2015), pp. 396–403. DOI: 10.9734/BJAST/2015/14975.
- [107] H. K. Kim, J. Park, Y. Choi and M. Choe. 'Virtual reality sickness questionnaire (VRSQ): Motion sickness measurement index in a virtual reality environment'. In: *Applied Ergonomics* 69 (2018), pp. 66–73. ISSN: 00036870. DOI: 10.1016/j.apergo.2017.12.016.
- [108] R. S. Kennedy, N. E. Lane, K. S. Berbaum and M. G. Lilienthal. 'Simulator Sickness Questionnaire: An Enhanced Method for Quantifying Simulator Sickness'. In: *The International Journal of Aviation Psychology* 3.3 (1993), pp. 203–220. ISSN: 1050-8414. DOI: 10.1207/s15327108ijap0303_3.
- [109] Ben Lang. *Valve VR on Steam Bounces Back to Nearly 2.8 Million Monthly-connected Headsets*. 2021. URL: <https://www.roadtovr.com/steam-survey-vr-headsets-on-steam-data-july-2021/> (visited on 12/11/2021).
- [110] G. Regal, R. Schatz, J. Schrammel and S. Suetter. 'VRate: A Unity3D Asset for integrating Subjective Assessment Questionnaires in Virtual Environments'. In: *2018 Tenth International Conference on Quality of Multimedia Experience (QoMEX)*. IEEE, 2018, pp. 1–3. ISBN: 978-1-5386-2605-4. DOI: 10.1109/QoMEX.2018.8463296.